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MARS - Meteorological Archive and Retrieval System M1.9/2

MARS User Guide *(For Data Retrieval)*

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MARS - Meteorological Archival and Retrieval System M 1.9/2

MARS User Guide
(For Data Retrieval)

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European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts

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1 INTRODUCTION

MARS is ECMWF's Meteorological Archival and Retrieval System. This manual describes the MARS facilities for the retrieval of data from ECMWF's operational and other archives. MARS also provides an interface to the Cray on-line Fields Data Base (FDB), which contains data from the current forecast and most recent analysis cycles, and any retrieval request which can be met from the FDB will result automatically in MARS accessing the FDB. A new MARS for workstations has been introduced and is described in Appendix G.

Data can be in the same form as archived, or undergo various manipulations before being returned to the user. The operations on retrieved fields, which can be performed by MARS on behalf on the user are:

- * derive u- and v-wind components from archived vorticity and divergence;
- * reduce the triangular truncation of spherical harmonic fields from the archived resolution;
- * change resolution of Gaussian grid fields;
- * change resolution of latitude/longitude grids;
- * convert spherical harmonics to Gaussian or latitude/longitude grids;
- * convert Gaussian to latitude/longitude grids;
- * perform subarea extraction in conjunction with the above;
- * change number of bits used when packing data;
- * unpack retrieved data.

From 1 July 1985 until 9 December 1985 the edition of the GRIB code used to pack the fields was an extension of the original, Experimental WMO GRIB code, but these ECMWF extensions are not completely in line with those adopted since by WMO. Since this date the archive formats conform to WMO GRIB Code. Edition 0 was used until 17.9.92, when Edition 1 was introduced in the daily archives. Fields converted from the old archives, which have been re-archived in MARS, also conform to the Edition 0 standard. The unpacking software converts the Experimental Edition flag fields and code values to the Edition 1 standards. However, users must be aware that the Experimental Edition had no way of distinguishing between initialised and uninitialised analysis. The differences between the Experimental Edition, Edition 0 and Edition 1 of the GRIB code are in Appendix E.

All observations are stored in BUFR code. As the MARS system is developed and new facilities provided, users will be kept informed. To enable this development to be most suited to users' needs, comments and feedback on the usefulness or otherwise of system facilities/documentation are invited.

2 MARS LANGUAGE

The directives have the following format:

VERB (Parameter1=Value1).....(ParameterN=ValueN)

Parameters and values shown in brackets are optional - default values may be used. Also, some verbs do not have any associated parameters. Leading spaces and tab characters are ignored. Directives may be in upper or lower case or a mixture of both. MARS converts everything to upper case except filenames.

VERB	identifies action to be taken
PARAMETER	predefined keyword like PARAM or DATE
VALUE	value to be assigned to corresponding parameter.

The following is a list of VERBs recognised by the system.

- * MARS invokes the MARS system
- * HELP displays/prints help file
- * NEWS displays/prints system news
- * END normal exit from MARS system
- * CHECKOUT similar to END, but the only action taken is to check the commands
- * DEFAULT reset MARS default values
- * STATUS displays/prints status of MARS commands
- * READ take commands from named file
- * QUIT abandon session
- * RETRIEVE retrieval from archives.

2.1 Internal Commands

These commands do not have any associated meteorological parameters and values and are handled entirely on the worker machine, without any reference to the archive directories. Users need not concern themselves with the difference between internal and MARS commands (e.g. Retrieve) except to remember that only the MARS commands are kept in the logfile (see section 3.1).

Verbs may be abbreviated - the minimum abbreviations are shown underlined.

MARS format MARS (see section 3 for permitted parameters).

- READ** format READ,NAME="filename".
- This verb allows commands to be read from a file other than the terminal or standard input. The contents of a READ file can be a set of MARS commands, and/or a set of internal commands (other than a READ). Commands saved from a previous session can be added to those entered from the terminal.
- NEWS** No parameters.
- This command lists a special file containing the latest news about the MARS system.
- HELP** No parameters.
- This is the first level (level 0) of help available to interactive users. It gives a list of valid verbs and a description of the general syntax of the commands, and how to get the other levels of help.
- Level 1 gets all the valid PARAMETERS for a verb by typing the verb name, followed by a comma and a question mark, after the prompt --> RETRIEVE,?. A list of all valid parameters for the verb RETRIEVE is displayed at the terminal by this example.
- Level 2 gets all valid VALUES for a specific PARAMETER of a specific verb, by typing the verb name, followed by the parameter name, equal sign and a question mark, after the prompt --> RETRIEVE,LEVEL=?. All possible values for the parameter LEVEL, for the verb RETRIEVE are displayed by this example.
- Used in batch mode these commands cause the same information to be printed.
- DEFAULT** Format DEFAULT,VERB=verb-name
- This verb resets all default values for all parameters to their initial settings for the given MARS verb.
- STATUS** Format STATUS,VERB=verb-name
- This displays/prints the current default values for a specific MARS command, e.g. STATUS,VERB=RETRIEVE will show the current value for each RETRIEVE parameter.
- END** No parameters.
- This terminates the set of commands entered by the user. Normal processing follows.
- QUIT** No parameters.

Abandons the session. No further processing is done on any commands entered.

CHECKOUT No parameters.

This terminates the set of commands entered by the user. MARS processing is limited to semantic checking of commands.

2.2 MARS Commands

MARS commands are much longer than internal commands, and may be entered on any number of lines. All lines must end with a comma, except the last line of each command.

Parameter=value pairs are separated by commas. Parameter and value must appear on the same line, but if a list of values is too long to fit on one line it may be continued. In this case the separator / must be the last character on the line, indicating that the value list continues on the next line. Up to six continuation lines for a list of values are permitted.

In the following sections the parameters and values of the MARS commands are given. Values are predefined names, numeric values or user-supplied character strings when names cannot be predefined, e.g. file names. All user-supplied character strings must be enclosed between double or single quote characters. Where users must supply a numeric value, the character * is used to indicate this. Most parameters have initial default values.

For verbs, parameters and value names, only enough letters for unique identification are necessary, i.e. TYPE=FIRST GUESS can be shorted to TY=FI.

The minimum letters required are shown underlined. Internally, MARS uses standard abbreviations for the value names of the different parameters. These may also be specified by users. These standard abbreviations are shown enclosed () in section 2.3, but are valid for other commands as well. In general, these standard abbreviations consist of the initial letters of the words in the value name, e.g. PL for PRESSURE LEVELS.

Parameters may have a single value, a list of values, a range of values or ALL values may be specified in some cases. The letters s, l, r, a under each parameter name indicate which options are valid for that particular parameter. A list is specified by the user by using the separator /, and a range is indicated by using TO, as well as /. Lists of pressure levels must be specified in ascending height. All other lists (dates, times, forecast timesteps, etc.) must be given in numerically ascending order. Examples of the different formats for a value are:

*	Single	-	PARAM=T
*	List	-	TIME=00/12
*	Range	-	DATE=850805/TO/850810
*	All	-	LEVEL=ALL

2.3 Retrieve Directives

Format is RETRIEVE,Param1=Value1.....ParamN=ValueN

Users need not know how or where data is stored, but it is useful to know that observations and forecast data for the current month and previous month are always on-line, and that analysis, initialised analysis and first guess data for the current month and the previous three months are also on-line. The most recent 2 days of forecast and analysis cycle data are available from the Cray Fields Data Base. The location of other data depends on the frequency with which it is used. Users must provide the MARS system with sufficient information to identify the data and format needed. The necessary parameters, and the values they can take, are listed here in a number of different categories.

2.3.1 Identification parameters of archive

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Value</u>	<u>MARS abbreviation</u>
<u>CLASS</u> s	= <u>OPERATIONS</u>	(OD) (default)
	<u>RESEARCH</u>	(RD)
<u>TYPE</u> s	= <u>FIRST GUESS</u>	(FG)
	<u>ANALYSIS</u>	(AN)
	<u>INIT. ANALYSIS</u>	(IA) (default)
	<u>FORECAST</u>	(FC)
	<u>ERRORS IN ANALYSIS</u>	(EA)
	<u>ERRORS IN FIRST GUESS</u>	(EF)
	<u>CLIMATOLOGY</u>	(CL)
	<u>OBSERVATIONS</u>	(OB)
	<u>CONTROL FORECAST</u>	(CF)
	<u>PERTURBED FORECAST</u>	(PF)
	<u>CLUSTER MEANS</u>	(CM)
<u>CLUSTER STANDARD DEVIATIONS</u>	(CS)	

Identifies the type of data required.

<u>STREAM</u> s	= <u>DAILY ARCHIVE</u>	(DA) (default)
	<u>TOGA</u>	(TG)
	<u>CHERNOBYL</u>	(CH)
	<u>MONTHLY</u>	(MO)
	<u>BRACKNELL</u>	(EGRR)
	<u>WASHINGTON</u>	(KWBC)
	<u>OFFENBACH</u>	(EDZW)
	<u>PARIS</u>	(LFPW)
	<u>TOKYO</u>	(RJTD)
	<u>MONTREAL</u>	(CWAQ)
	<u>ENSEMBLE FORECASTS</u>	(EF)

Identifies the archive stream required.

<u>EXPVER</u> s	= * (Default is 1, Operational Version)	
	"...."	

Identifies the version or experiment. See sections 5, 6 and 8 for details of archive contents and identifiers.

<u>LEVTYPE</u>	= <u>SURFACE</u>	(SFC)
----------------	------------------	-------

s **PRESSURE LEVELS** (PL) (default)
 MODEL LEVELS (ML)

Indicates the type of level.

LEVELIST = * (DEFAULT 1000/850/700/500/400/300)
s,l,a ALL
 OFF

List of levels required - it defaults to **OFF** if **LEVTYPE** is **SFC**.
If the log of surface pressure is the only parameter being retrieved from a model level archive, it must be set to 1 (in this case if set to **ALL** it also returns one field).

REPRES = **SPHERICAL HARMONICS** (SH) (default)
s GAUSSIAN GRID (GG)
 LATITUDE LONGITUDE GRID (LL)
 BUFR (BUFR)

Identifies data representation used in the archives. It has no effect on retrieved data.

Use **SH** for upper-air data (see exception below), **GG** for surface data from the daily archive stream for data from 18Z on 20.4.83 onwards (**LL** before that date). Use **LL** for all data in the TOGA archive, data from other centres and for errors in analysis and errors in first guess. Use **BUFR** for observations.

Exception.

Starting from 4/4/95, the following parameters are archived in **GG** format:
Q (133) on model levels and pressure levels and **CLWC** (246), **CIWC** (247), **CC** (248) on model levels. See section 6 for details.

2.3.2 Date and time parameters

DATE = * (date in yymmdd format = 6 digits) (for Monthly Means data dd=00)
s,l,r or
 * (date relative to current date, e.g. -1 for yesterday)
 or
 name of month, e.g. January (for **TYPE=CL** only).

Default is current date. Gives date of analysis or forecast base date.

For **DATE**, an interval in days may be specified for a range of values (not valid for access to Cray Fields Data Base), e.g.

DATE=880102/to/880110/BY/2

The default interval is 1 day.

TIME = * (time in hhmm format).
s,l,r Default for hh is 12, for mm 00.

For observations, if mm is omitted in the first time of a range of times, it defaults to 01,

e.g.

06/TO/12 becomes 0601/TO/1200.

Gives time for observations, analysis, forecast base time, or first guess verifying time.

For **TIME**, an interval in hours may be specified for a range of values (not valid for access to Cray Fields Data Base) e.g.

TIME=00/TO/18/BY/6

The default interval is 6 hours.

STEP = * (hours)
ALL
 s,l,r,a Default is 00. (Interpreted as 06 for first guess fields for backward compatibility.)

Gives forecast time step from forecast base time or length of forecast which verifies at first guess time see Appendix A, Example 1 (b)). 00 must be used for all other data.

For **STEP**, an interval in hours may be specified for a range of values (not valid for access to Cray Fields Data Base), e.g.

STEP=12/TO/240/BY/12

The default interval is 12 hours.

2.3.3 Target file parameters

TARGET = "filename"
 s
 There is no default target filename.

This specifies the file where the retrieved data is to go.

If it is required to make only one target file from a number of retrieve requests, the same "filename" should be specified in each retrieval request. (See sections 3.3 and 3.4 for details of target files.)

CFSPATH = "/uid/COS/filename"
 s "filename"

Default is for MARS to generate a unique CFS filename.

uid is the 3 letter user identifier. If only "filename" is given, MARS generates the full pathname, using the first 3 letters of the jobname as the user identifier.

When users specify a CFS filename into which the retrieved data will be stored, the

retention period is one week. If a longer retention period is required, users can use the ECFILE command **MODIFY** to extend it. Any subsequent access to MARS which specifies the same CFS filename will result in the existing CFS file being transferred to the user's target file. If the CFS filename is not specified by the user, a temporary file will be used by MARS.

Users jobs will fail if the user does not have the necessary access rights to the CFS pathname specified in the directives. CFS FILENAMES MUST BE UNIQUE in each individual request. When a filename is given, MARS will return the file specified, if it exists, regardless of any other parameter in the request. A warning message is always issued if an existing file is returned. Use of the CFS pathname parameter prohibits access to the on-line Fields Data Base for current data.

Use of this feature is recommended, especially for multiple requests, as recovery in the event of a retry is speeded up considerably by using the existing permanent files, instead of having to recreate the lost temporary ones.

2.3.4 Meteorological parameters

PARAM = Field name
s,l,a abbreviation e.g. (Z) (default)
*
ALL

For field name, abbreviation or code number see section 7.1.

Numbers may not be mixed with names or abbreviations in lists of values.

If u- and v-wind components for upper-air fields are required, these may be specified and will automatically be calculated from archived values of vorticity and divergence (u and v must always be requested as a pair).

If both vorticity and divergence and u and v are requested, an error message about repeated parameters will be received.

QBSTYPE = observation type
s,l,a observation subtype
abbreviation
*
ALL
SD Satellite data (all)
NSD Non-satellite data (all)

For observation types, subtypes, abbreviations and numbers see section 7.2.

2.3.5 Data manipulation parameters

These parameters allow values to be specified which result in various operations being performed, on behalf of the user, on fields retrieved from the archives. Examples of their use are given in Appendix A.

The following facilities are available:

- * reduce the triangular truncation of spherical harmonic fields from the archived resolution;
- * change resolution of Gaussian grid fields;
- * change resolution of latitude/longitude grids;
- * convert spherical harmonics to Gaussian or latitude/longitude grids;
- * convert Gaussian to latitude/longitude grids;
- * perform subarea extraction in conjunction with the above;
- * change number of bits used when packing data;
- * unpack retrieved data.

RESOL = **ARCHIVED VALUE** (AV) (default)
 s **OFF** (O)

Specifies the triangular truncation to be used when writing fields to the target file or when performing any extraction or conversion. Conversion to u- and v-wind components always uses the full archived resolution.

* is a positive integer, e.g. 63.

OFF should be used if the archive being accessed is not stored in spherical harmonic format. This suppresses printing of the value, which is otherwise ignored.

If **RESOL=OFF** is specified for data archived in spherical harmonic format, **RESOL=AV** is used, and a warning message is printed.

AREA = **GLOBAL** (G) (default)
 s,l **EUROPE** (E)
 Northern Hemisphere octant 1 [N1]
 Northern Hemisphere octant 2 [N2]
 Northern Hemisphere octant 3 [N3]
 Northern Hemisphere octant 4 [N4]
 Southern Hemisphere octant 1 [S1]
 Southern Hemisphere octant 2 [S2]
 Southern Hemisphere octant 3 [S3]
 Southern Hemisphere octant 4 [S4]
 */**/*

Output area definition, for fields or observations.

Four values (3 decimal places allowed) to allow user defined subarea as North/West/South/East. (Use negative values for Western longitudes and Southern latitudes.) If South > North the values are swapped and a warning message issued.

EUROPE is the same as 73.5/-27.0/33.0/45.0.

N1 - 45W to 45E
 N2 - 135W to 45W
 N3 - 135E to 135W
 N4 - 45E to 135E

S1 to S4 is the same but for Southern Hemisphere.

If the area specified is inconsistent with the grid mesh requested, the area is extended as necessary to ensure consistency (packed or unpacked data formats include the coordinates of the area actually provided). A warning message of changes made is given.

An overlap of boundaries is not permitted, e.g. 90/-180/0/180 is illegal.

Retrieval of archived spherical harmonic data, without conversion to grid point must have AREA=GLOBAL. Any other value is ignored, and a warning message issued.

For observations two additional parameters are available to enable selection by WMO Block or Station numbers.

BLOCK = *
s,1 OFF (0) (default)

WMO Block number(s)
e.g. 02 or 01/02/06

IDENT = *
s,1 OFF (0) (default)

WMO Station number (with Block number)
e.g. 03953 or 03952/03953/03955

If a station number is given, BLOCK and AREA values are ignored. If a block number is given the AREA value is ignored.

GRID = A RCHIVED VALUE (AV)
s,1 O FF (0) (default)
*
/

Specifies required output grid mesh. If the grid mesh specified cannot be handled by the interpolation software, it is reduced to one which can. Minimum mesh is .5/.5. A warning message is printed.

A single positive integer (e.g. 48) specifies the number of lines of latitude between the Pole and the Equator in Gaussian output fields.

Two values (3 decimal places allowed) give E-W and N-S increments for output latitude/longitude grid.

GRID=OFF should be used if archived spherical harmonic data is required in spherical harmonic format.

If GRID=OFF is specified for data archived as grid values, GRID=AV is used and a warning message printed.

ACCURACY = **NORMAL** (N) (default)
 s **REDUCED** (R)
LOW (L)
 *

Specifies the number of bits to be used for each GRIB coded packed value.

NORMAL is 24 bits for geopotential and height. It is also 24 for temperature and log of surface pressure in T213. 16 bits for other parameters. Since the introduction of complex packing of Spherical Harmonics data on 23/8/94, 16 bits are used for all parameters. These are the values used in the operational and research archives. In the TOGA archive all parameters are in 16 bits.

Derived u and v values also use 24 bits.

REDUCED is **NORMAL** - 8 bits.

LOW is 8 bits.

An integer value may also be given.

FORMAT = **UNPACKED** (U)
 s **PACKED** (P) (default)

Packed values are in WMO FM-92 GRIB code or FM-94 BUFR code.

Utilities for handling packed and unpacked data are described in section 4.

Observations are currently available on the Cray only in packed format.

2.3.6 Other parameters

LAUNCH = "filename" (no default)
 s

The job contained in the specified CRAY file is launched, when retrieval is complete.

COSTONLY = **YES** (Y)
 s **NO** (N) (default)

If **COSTONLY=YES** is specified, no data is retrieved. An informative message is printed showing how many tapes need to be accessed to honour the retrieval request.

COSTONLY=YES and **COSTONLY=NO** may not be mixed in the same set of requests.

USE = **NORMAL** (N) (default)
 s **FREQUENT** (F)
INFREQUENT (I)

Specifies the likely frequency of future accesses to the data. This is for future use.

3 USER INTERFACES (CRAY)

The MARS User Interface consists of

- * a language in which the users specify requests to the system;
- * a set of procedures to support the language and drive the system.

MARS is invoked on the Cray Y-MP by using the command MARS (or mars) in a script, or typing it at a terminal.

3.1 Edit mode

This is an interactive utility to enable users to build up a file of directives for later use in a retrieval job. To use it, enter the following at a terminal:

```
mars -e
```

The user is first prompted to enter a filename. Edited requests are written to this logfile.

A command processor is used to drive the dialogue between MARS and the user in a helpful way, providing assistance to correct errors and minimising the amount of typing required. It is not necessary to type all the words of a command in full. Provided enough letters are typed to give a unique entry, such an entry is accepted. If an abbreviation used gives rise to ambiguity, the command processor will respond with an error message and display the different interpretations of the abbreviated entry.

This interactive facility allows users to enter instructions to MARS one after the other in a purely interactive way, or to use a READ file, or both. In normal interactive execution the user types in the requests in response to prompts from the system. If a command does not fit on one line and must be continued, a comma must be used at the end of the line to indicate a continuation line follows. When a complete command has been entered, MARS displays the command with the verb and parameters fully expanded and with the standard abbreviations for corresponding values. The user then has the option to accept or reject the command displayed. If accepted, the command is written to the MARS logfile, before another command can be entered.

Most parameters have initial default values associated with them, the exceptions being the filename strings. When any value is altered by the user, this value becomes the default value for the next request from the user.

MARS requests may include comments. Comment lines start with an *.

If the session is terminated by either the END or CHECKOUT command, then the user is left with a file of directives, syntactically checked, for later use in a retrieval job. If the session is terminated by entering the QUIT command, no directive file is kept.

3.2 Active mode

The command to call MARS (interactive or batch) to retrieve data is

`mars [-o overwrite] [-f altfilename] [filename]`

- **overwrite** is a string (enclosed in single or double quote marks) of parameter=value pairs, separated by commas, to be used to overwrite those in the directives;

- **filename** is the file containing the MARS directives. If it is not specified, standard input is used;

- **altfilename** is an alternative file, containing MARS directives to be read before those in filename or standard input.

If this alternative file contains an END command, main file of directives (or standard input) will not be read.

Each such call to MARS can contain a number of retrieval requests, which can specify the same or different target files. Users' retrieval requests are printed, once exactly as the user has entered them and then, as interpreted by MARS with default values added (see Appendix A).

MARS uses Fortran unit numbers 1-12.

EXAMPLES

1. UNICOS command to read directives from job input stream

```
mars << *eor
retrieve, date=900815, type=fc, target="/tmp/mah/myfile"
end
*eor
```

2. UNICOS command to read all directives from the file 'dirfile'

```
mars dirfile
```

3. UNICOS command to read some directives from the file 'dirfile' and the rest from the input stream

```
mars -f dirfile << *eor
retrieve, date=-3
end
*eor
```

4. UNICOS command to read some directives from the file 'dirfile' and the rest from file 'maindirs'

```
mars -f dirfile maindirs
```

5. UNICOS command to use directives in the file 'dirfile', overwriting some parameter values

```
mars -o "date=900815, time=12, step=240" dirfile
```


6. Using shell variables

```
#  
# Set variable THE_DATE  
#  
THE_DATE=900815  
#  
mars << *eor  
retrieve,date=$THE_DATE,target="/tmp/mah/mine"  
end  
*eor
```

```
# File 'dirfile' contains directives  
# Set variable THE_DATE  
#  
THE_DATE=900815  
#  
mars -o "date=$THE_DATE" dirfile
```

7. Using stream editor and piping

If file 'myfile' contains

```
retrieve, date=yymmdd,target="/tmp/mah/abc"  
end
```

then `yymmdd` can be substituted and MARS called by the command

```
sed -e 's/yymmdd/900815/' <myfile | mars
```

3.3 Target files (fields)

The user is provided with one file of data for one or more retrieval requests. If the named target file exists before execution of the MARS request, it is deleted. A warning message is printed.

Retrieved data comes in a specific sequence. A retrieval request writes data to the user's target file thus

```
DO 500 DATE = DATE1 TO DATE2  
DO 400 TIME = TIME1 TO TIME2  
DO 300 LEVEL = LEVEL1 TO LEVEL 2  
DO 200 PARAM = PARAM1 TO PARAM2  
WRITE FIELD TO TARGET FILE  
200 CONTINUE  
300 CONTINUE  
400 CONTINUE  
500 CONTINUE
```

The order in which dates, times and levels are requested is controlled (see 2.2) and MARS itself sorts the meteorological parameters in ascending field code order before extracting any data, except from Cray

FDB. Field codes are given in section 7.1.

For example, the command

```
RET,DATE=850925/850926,TIME=12,LEVEL=1000/700,PARAM=T/Z,TARGET="MYFILE"
```

would result in a target file (MYFILE) with data in the order

```
Z      1000 1200 850925
T      1000 1200 890925
Z      700 1200 850925
T      700 1200 850925
Z      1000 1200 850926
T      1000 1200 850926
Z      700 1200 850926
T      700 1200 850926
```

whereas the commands

```
RET,DATE=850925/850926,TIME=12,LEVEL=1000/700,PARAM=T,TARGET="MYFILE"
RET,DATE=850925/850926,TIME=12,LEVEL=1000/700,PARAM=Z
```

would result in a target file (MYFILE) with data in the order

```
T      1000 1200 850925
T      700 1200 850925
T      1000 1200 850926
T      700 1200 850926
Z      1000 1200 850925
Z      700 1200 850925
Z      1000 1200 850926
Z      700 1200 850926
```

Unpacked formats are 3 times longer (surface fields and geopotential) or 4 times longer (other upper-air parameters) so large numbers of fields should not be retrieved in unpacked format.

3.4 Target files (observations)

The user is provided with one file of data for one or more retrieval requests. The Cray target file is always in packed (BUFR) format. The data comes in the sequence shown below, for each requested time period.

MARS abbreviation

Observation type

LSD	Land surface data
SSD	Sea surface data
VSNS	Vertical soundings (not satellite)
SLNS	Single level upper-air (not satellite)
OD	Oceanographic data
VSS	Vertical soundings (satellite)
SLS	Single level upper-air (satellite).

4 UTILITIES

4.1 Field Data

From 1 July to 9 December 1985 all data was stored in the Experimental Edition of WMO GRIB code (with some ECMWF extensions). For other dates the formats conform to the GRIB Edition 0 up to 17.9.91, Edition 1 since. Appendix E contains the GRIB code editions differences. However, ECMWF uses its own local Code Table 2, the meteorological parameters code. In general, the MARS (GRIB) field codes used are 128 + Cray post-processing field codes. Details of the meteorological parameter codes used by ECMWF are in section 7.1. To facilitate handling on machines with different word lengths each record in GRIB code is made a multiple of 120 octets in length.

Software exists to unpack the fields and to print the product and grid definition sections etc. The routines GRIBEX, GRPRS1, GRPRS2, GRPRS3 and GRPRS4 can handle data in all Editions. The Cray routines are held on the binary library \$EMOSLIB.

4.1.1 Routines for packed format data

The target files of packed data can be read with **BUFFER IN**. Unpacking GRIB data is done by calling the subroutine **GRIBEX**, with the parameters shown below (it is possible to decode the identification blocks without the necessity to decode the data). To accommodate the surface fields arrays should be dimensioned as KGRIB(34000) and PSEC4 (135000), but for upper-air fields KGRIB(4700) and PSEC4 (47000) are sufficient. These sizes refer to data as archived in T213 and N160. If data conversion (e.g. spherical harmonic to grid-point) has been requested, they may need to be enlarged. If arrays are too small, GRIBEX returns an error code and indicates the minimum length required. See example of use in Appendix B.

```
      SUBROUTINE GRIBEX (KSEC0,KSEC1,KSEC2,PSEC2,KSEC3,PSEC3,KSEC4,
C          PSEC4,KLENP,KGRIB,KLENG,KWORD,HOPER,KRET)
C
C**** GRIBEX - Coding and decoding of GRIB format data.
C
C  Purpose.
C  -----
C
C      1) Code data in FM-92 GRIB code, Edition 1.
C      2) Decode data from FM-92 GRIB code.
C      3) Decode only identification sections of GRIB
C         coded data i.e. Sections 0, 1 and 2.
C      4) Return length of GRIB message, in bytes, and GRIB
C         Edition number only.
C
C      A number of options exist when coding or decoding -
C      see values allowed for requested function, HOPER, below.
C
C      Decoding functions work on Experimental Edition,
C      Edition 0 and Edition 1 of GRIB code. Decoded values
C      for Sections 0 to 2 are always in Edition 1 format.
C
C** Interface.
```



```
C -----  
C  
C CALL GRIBEX (KSEC0,KSEC1,KSEC2,PSEC2,KSEC3,PSEC3,KSEC4,  
C C PSEC4,KLENP,KGRIB,KLENG,KWORD,HOPER,KRET)  
C  
C Integer K  
C Real P.  
C Logical O.  
C Character H.  
C
```

```
C Input Parameters for all functions.  
C -----  
C
```

```
C HOPER - Requested function.  
C
```

```
C 'C' To code data in GRIB code, with or  
C without bitmaps.  
C
```

```
C 'D' To decode data from GRIB code. If  
C ECMWF pseudo-Grib data is encountered,  
C only sections 0 and 1 are decoded and  
C the return code is set to -6.  
C
```

```
C 'I' To decode only identification  
C sections 0, 1 and 2 of GRIB or  
C pseudo-Grib data.  
C
```

```
C 'L' Return length of GRIB message, in  
C bytes, and GRIB Edition number only.  
C Length does not include any bytes  
C added to round message length to a  
C multiple of 120 bytes. Works also for  
C pseudo-Grib data.  
C
```

```
C 'R' To decode data from GRIB code, and if  
C a quasi-regular Gaussian grid is  
C encountered, convert it to regular.  
C
```

```
C 'S' To decode initialised analysis data  
C from GRIB code, and if data is in the  
C Experimental Edition of GRIB, set the  
C Time Range Indicator flag. In the  
C Experimental Edition there was no  
C distinction between initialised and  
C uninitialised analyses.  
C
```

```
C 'X' To extract data values for up to 4  
C points from a GRIB coded Gaussian or  
C
```


C Latitude/longitude field, without
C unpacking the data at other points.
C See KSEC4.
C

C KLENP - Length of array PSEC4.
C

C KLENG - Length of array KGRIB.
C

C KRET - Response to error indicator.
C 0 Abort if error encountered.
C Negative return codes are
C informative and do not cause
C an abort.
C Non- zero, Return to calling routine
C even if error encountered.
C

C Input parameters for coding function.
C Output Parameters for decoding functions.
C -----
C

C KSEC1 - Integer parameters of Section 1 (Product
C Definition Section) of GRIB code.
C Integer array of at least 25 words.
C

C If Section 1 of the GRIB code contains
C data for ECMWF local use, KSEC1 should
C be sized accordingly e.g. 53 + N, where
C N is the number of ensemble forecasts.
C

C Word Contents.
C -----
C

- C 1 Version number of Code Table 2.
- C 2 Identification of centre (Code Table 0).
- C 3 Generating process identification number
C (allocated by originating centre).
- C 4 Grid definition (NNN - Catalogue number
C of grid used by originating centre. See
C Volume B of publication WMO - No.9).
- C 5 Flag indication relative to Section 2
C (Grid Description Section) and Section
C 3 (Bit Map Section). Code Table 1.
C Valid values are:-
C

C Decimal
C

C	value	Meaning
C	-----	-----
C	0	Sections 2 and 3 omitted.
C	128	Section 2 included, Section 3 omitted.
C	64	Section 2 omitted, Section 3 included.
C	192	Sections 2 and 3 included.
C	6	Indicator of parameter (Code Table 2).
C	7	Indicator of type of level (Code Table 3).
C	8	Height, pressure etc. of level (Code Table 3). Single level or top of layer.
C	9	Height, pressure etc. of level (Code Table 3). Bottom of layer, if word 6 indicates a layer.
C	10	Year of century)
C	11	Month) Reference time of data -
C	12	Day) Date and time of start of
C	13	Hour) averaging or accumulation
C	14	Minute) period.
C	15	Indicator of unit of time (Code Table 4).
C	16	P1 - Period of time (number of time units) (0 for analyses or initialised analyses).
C	17	P2 - Period of time (number of time units); or time interval between successive analyses, initialised analyses or forecasts undergoing averaging or accumulation; otherwise set to zero.
C	18	Time range indicator (Code Table 5).
C	19	Number included in average, when time range indicator indicates an average or accumulation; otherwise set to zero.
C	20	Number missing from average, when time range indicator indicates an average or accumulation; otherwise set to zero.
C	21	Century of reference time of data.
C	22	Reserved. set to 0.
C	23	Decimal scale factor.
C	24	Flag field to indicate local use in Section 1. 0 - No local use of section 1. 1 - Local use of section 1.
C	25-36	Reserved for WMO reserved fields. Set to 0.
C	37	ECMWF local usage identifier. This is a number which indicates the contents of words 38-nn. 1 - ECMWF local GRIB use definition 1. 2 - ECMWF local GRIB use definition 1.

- C 8 Lo2 - Longitude of last grid point.
- C 9 Di - i direction increment.
- C 10 Dj - j direction increment.
- C 11 Scanning mode flags (Code Table 8).
- C 12 Number of vertical coordinate parameters.
- C 13 Latitude of the southern pole of rotation.
- C 14 Longitude of the southern pole of rotation.
- C 15 Latitude of the pole of stretching.
- C 16 Longitude of the pole of stretching.
- C 17 0, Regular grid.
- C 1, Quasi-regular (reduced) grid.
- C 18 Earth flag.
- C Valid values are:-
- C
- C Decimal
- C value Meaning
- C -----
- C 0 Earth assumed spherical with
- C radius of 6367.47 km.
- C 64 Earth assumed oblate spheroidal
- C with size as determined by IAU in
- C 1965:
- C (6378.160km,6356.775km,f=1/297.0)
- C
- C 19 Components flag.
- C Valid values are:-
- C
- C Decimal
- C value Meaning
- C -----
- C 0 Resolved u and v components of
- C vector quantities relative to
- C easterly and northerly directions.
- C
- C 8 Resolved u and v components of
- C vector quantities relative to the
- C defined grid in the direction of
- C increasing x and y (or i and j)
- C coordinates respectively.
- C
- C 20-22 Reserved. Set to 0.
- C 23-nn Number of points along each parallel
- C in a Quasi-regular grid. Number of parallels
- C is given by Nj above.
- C or
- C Number of points along each meridian
- C in a Quasi-regular grid. Number of meridians
- C is given by Ni above.
- C

Scanning mode flags (Code Table 8) indicate whether points are consecutive on a meridian or a parallel.

Notes:- 1) Increments are in millidegrees.

Word Contents for Gaussian grids.

- 1 Data representation type (Code Table 6).
 - 2 Ni - Number of points along a parallel.
Cannot be used for quasi-regular grids.
 - 3 Nj - Number of points along a meridian.
 - 4 La1 - Latitude of first grid point.
 - 5 Lo1 - Longitude of first grid point.
 - 6 Resolution flag.
Valid values are:-
- | Decimal value | Meaning |
|---------------|--|
| 0 | Direction increments not given.
Used for quasi-regular grids, but can also be used for regular grids. |
| 128 | Direction increments given.
Grids must be regular. |
- 7 La2 - Latitude of last grid point.
 - 8 Lo2 - Longitude of last grid point.
 - 9 Di - i direction increment.
Cannot be used for quasi-regular grids.
 - 10 N - Number of parallels between a Pole and the Equator.
 - 11 Scanning mode flags (Code Table 8).
 - 12 Number of vertical coordinate parameters.
 - 13 Latitude of the southern pole of rotation.
 - 14 Longitude of the southern pole of rotation.
 - 15 Latitude of the pole of stretching.
 - 16 Longitude of the pole of stretching.
 - 17 0, Regular grid.
1, Quasi-regular (reduced) grid.
 - 18 Earth flag.
Valid values are:-

Decimal

- 16 Longitude of the pole of stretching.
17-22 Reserved. Set to 0.

Word Contents for Polar Stereographic.

- 1 Data representation type (Code Table 6).
2 Nx - Number of points along X-axis.
3 Ny - Number of points along Y-axis.
4 La1 - Latitude of first grid point.
5 Lo1 - Longitude of first grid point.
6 Reserved. Set to 0. Resolution flag is not applicable to Polar stereographic.
7 LoV - Orientation of the grid i.e. the longitude of the meridian which is parallel to the Y-axis along which latitude increases as the Y-coordinate increases.
8 Reserved. Set to 0.
9 Dx - X-direction grid length.
10 Dy - Y-direction grid length.
11 Scanning mode flag (Code Table 8).
12 Number of vertical coordinate parameters.
13 Projection centre flag.
0, North pole is on projection plane.
1, South pole is on projection plane. ??????
128, South pole is on projection plane. ????
- 14-16 Reserved. Set to 0.
17 0, Regular grid.
1, Quasi-regular (reduced) grid.
18 Earth flag.
Valid values are:-

Decimal value	Meaning
---------------	---------

- | | |
|----|--|
| 0 | Earth assumed spherical with radius of 6367.47 km. |
| 64 | Earth assumed oblate spheroidal with size as determined by IAU in 1965:
(6378.160km,6356.775km,f=1/297.0) |

- 19 Components flag.
Valid values are:-

Decimal	Meaning
---------	---------


```

C      ! ENTIRE FIELD IS MISSING. All values in PSEC4
C      ! are 0. This is an ECMWF convention - coded
C      ! data has scale factor, exponent and mantissa
C      ! of reference value with all bits set to 1.
C      !
C      !!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!
C
C      2  Number of bits used for each packed value.
C      3  Type of data. Used only if Section 2 is
C          not included when coding data.
C          0 - Grid point data.
C          128 - Spherical harmonic coefficients.
C      4  Type of packing.
C          0 - Simple packing.
C          64 - Complex or second order packing.
C            (Not implemented)
C      5  Data representation.
C          0 - Floating point data.
C          32 - Integer data.
C      6  Additional flags indicator.
C          0 - No additional flags.
C          16 - additional flags.
C      7  Reserved. Set to 0.
C      8  Number of values indicator.
C          0 - Single datum at each grid point.
C          64 - Matrix of values at each grid point.
C      9  Secondary bit maps indicator.
C          0 - No secondary bit maps.
C          32 - Secondary bit maps present.
C     10  Values width indicator.
C          0 - Second order values constant width.
C          16 - Second order values different widths.
C            (Not implemented)
C     11  Number of bits for second order values,
C          when of constant width.
C            (Not implemented)
C     12-15  Reserved for WMO reserved flag fields.
C            Set to 0.
C     12-33  Reserved. Set to 0.
C
C          Words 34 to 42 are used only for the 'X'
C          function. Scanning mode must be from West
C          to East and from North to South.
C     34  Number of points (maximum 4) from which
C          data is to be unpacked.
C     35  Number of latitude row of first value.
C     36  Number of longitude point of first value.
C     37  Number of latitude row of second value.
C     38  Number of longitude point of second value.
    
```


C Informative codes for decoding functions.
 C
 C -2 , Bit-map encountered with all bits
 C set to 1. Array PSEC4 contains all
 C real data values.
 C -3 , Predetermined bit-map encountered.
 C Data has not been fully decoded i.e.
 C array PSEC4 contains only real data
 C values. The user must use this data
 C in conjunction with the defined
 C bit-map.
 C -4 , Bit-map encountered. The data has
 C been fully decoded i.e. array PSEC4
 C contains real values and missing
 C data indicators where appropriate.
 C -6 , ECMWF pseudo-grib data encountered.
 C
 C Error codes.
 C
 C 0 , No error encountered.
 C
 C Positive numbers indicate errors.
 C Self-explanatory messages are printed.
 C
 C

4.1.2 Routines for unpacked data

The target files of unpacked data can be read with **BUFFER IN**. To accommodate the surface fields, the input array should be 135000 words long, but for upper-air data 34000 is sufficient. Again, these sizes refer to fields as archived (see 4.1.1). To extract the section 1 and 2 information and the field values the following subroutines are used. See Appendix C for an example of their use.

SUBROUTINE GETFB2 (KLFB2,PFB2,KLENG,KARRAY,KPR,KRET)

***** GETFB2 - Extract real values from section 2 of GRIB code.

Purpose

Get real values from section 2 of unpacked GRIB or pseudo-grib records, retrieved from MARS.

** Interface

CALL GETFB2 (KLFB2,PFB2,KLENG,KARRAY,KPR,KRET)

INTEGER	K.
REAL	P.
LOGICAL	O.
CHARACTER	H.

Input parameters

PFB2 - Array to receive section 2 values
KLENG - Length of this array
KARRAY - Array containing unpacked record
KPR - Debug print switch
0 no printout
1 debug printout
2 print values extracted
KRET - Abort/no abort when error found
0 abort if error found
non-zero no abort if error found

Output parameters

PFB2 - Array containing values from section 2
KLFB2 - Number of values in this array
KRET - Error return code
0 no error encountered
1 target array too small

SUBROUTINE GETFPD (KFPD,PFPD,KLEN,KARAY,KPR,KRET)

*****GETFPD - Extract data from unpacked GRIB record.

Purpose

Get floating point data from record of unpacked GRIB or pseudo-grib data.

**** Interface**

CALL GETFPD (KFPD,PFPD,KLEN,KARAY,KPR,KRET)

INTEGER K.
REAL P.
LOGICAL O.
CHARACTER H.

Input parameters

PFPD - Array to receive floating point data
KLEN - Length of this array
KARAY - Array containing unpacked record
KPR - Debug print switch
0 no printout
1 debug printout
KRET - About/no abort when error found
0 abort if error found
non-zero no abort on error.

Output parameters

KRET - Error return code
0 no error encountered
1 target array too small
PFPP - Floating point data
KFPD - Number of values in this array.

SUBROUTINE GETIB1 (KLIB1,KIB1,KLENG,KARRAY,KPR,KRET)

*****GETIB1 - Get values from section 1 of GRIB code.

Purpose

Get integer values from section 1 of unpacked GRIB or pseudo-grib records, retrieved from MARS.

****** Interface

CALL GETIB1 (KLIB1,KIB1,KLENG,KARRAY,KPR,KRET)

INTEGER K.
REAL P.
LOGICAL O.
CHARACTER H.

Input parameters

KIB1 - Array to receive section 1 values
KLENG - Length of this array
KARRAY - Array containing unpacked record
KPR - Debut print switch
0 no printout
1 debug printout
2 print section 1 values
KRET - Abort/no abort when error found
0 abort if error found
non-zero no abort when error found.

Output parameters

KIB1 - Array containing values from section 1
KLIB1 - Number of values in this array
KRET - Error return code
0 no error encountered
1 target array too small.

SUBROUTINE GETIB2 (KLIB2,KIB2,KLENG,KARRAY,KPR,KRET)

***** GETIB2 - Extract integer values from section 2 of GRIB record.

Purpose

Get integer values from section 2 of unpacked GRIB or pseudo-grib records, retrieved from MARS.

**** Interface**

CALL GETIB2 (KLIB2,KIB2,KLENG,KARRAY,KPR,KRET)

INTEGER K.
REAL P.
LOGICAL O.
CHARACTER H.

Input parameters

KIB2 - Array to receive section 2 values
KLENG - Length of this array
KARRAY - Array containing unpacked record
KPR - Debug print switch
 0 no printout
 1 debug printout
 2 print section 2 values
KRET - Abort/no abort when error found
 0 abort if error found
 non-zero no abort if error found.

Output parameters

KIB2 - Array containing values from section 2
KLIB2 - Number of values in this array
KRET - Error return code
 0 no error encountered
 1 target array too small.

4.1.3 Printing routines

When a field has been unpacked the various sections can be printed if required.

CALL GRPRS0 (KSEC0) To print section 0.
CALL GRPRS1 (KSEC0,KSEC1) To print section 1.
CALL GRPRS2 (KSEC0,KSEC2,PSEC2) To print section 2.
CALL GRPRS3 (KSEC0,KSEC3,PSEC3) To print section 3.
CALL GRPRS4 (KSEC0,KSEC4,PSEC4) To print section 4.

Sample output is shown below;-

Section 0 - Indicator Section.

Length of GRIB message (octets). 138114
GRIB Edition Number. 1

Section 1 - Product Definition Section.

Code Table 2 Version Number.	128
Originating centre identifier.	98
Model identification.	40
Grid definition.	255
Flag (Code Table 1)	10000000
Parameter identifier (Code Table 2).	129
Type of level (Code Table 3).	100
Value 1 of level (Code Table 3).	1000
Value 2 of level (Code Table 3).	0
Year of data.	92
Month of data.	12
Day of data.	17
Hour of data.	12
Minute of data.	0
Time unit (Code Table 4).	1
Time range one.	0
Time range two.	0
Time range indicator (Code Table 5)	1
Number averaged.	0
Number missing from average.	0
Century of data.	20
Units decimal scaling factor.	0

Section 2 - Grid Description Section.

Data representation type (Table 6).	50
J - Pentagonal resolution parameter.	213
K - Pentagonal resolution parameter.	213
M - Pentagonal resolution parameter.	213
Representation type (Table 9)	1
Representation mode (Table 10)	1
Not used	0
Number of vertical coordinate parameters	0

Section 4 - Binary Data Section.

Number of data values coded/decoded	46010
Number of bits per data value	24
Type of data indicator	128
Type of packing indicator	0
Type of data representation	0
Additional flags indicator	0
Reserved	0
Number of values indicator	0
Secondary bit-maps indicator	0
Values width indicator.	0
Number of bits for second order values	0

4.2 Observations

All observations are stored in WMO BUFR code.

Software exists to unpack the data and print the different sections. The unpacking routine is BUFREX and print routines are BUPRS0, BUPRS1, BUPRS2 and BUPRS3. The Cray routines are held in the binary library \$EMOSLIB.

4.2.1 Routines for packed BUFR data

The target files of packed BUFR data can be read with **BUFFER IN**. Unpacking the observations is done by calling BUFREX with the parameters shown below.

```
      SUBROUTINE BUFREX(KBUFL,KBUFF,KSUP,KSEC0,KSEC1,KSEC2,KSEC3,KSEC4,
2          KELEM,CNAMES,CUNITS,KVALS,VALUES,CVALS,KERR)
C
C**** *BUFREX*
C
C
C  PURPOSE.
C  -----
C      Decode Bufr message into fully expanded form; returning
C  information relevant for all bufr sections, expanded values,
C  their names and units.
C
C
C**  INTERFACE.
C  -----
C
C      *CALL* *BUFREX(KBUFL,KBUFF,KSUP,KSEC0,KSEC1,KSEC2,KSEC3,KSEC4
C 1          KELEM,CNAMES,CUNITS,KVALS,VALUES,CVALS,KERR)*
C
C  INPUT:
C      *KBUFL* - length of bufr message (words)
C      *KBUFF* - array containing bufr message
C      *KELEM* - dimension of CNAMES, CUNITS array
C      *KVALS* - dimension of VALUES array
C  OUTPUT:
C      *KSUP* - array containing supplementary information
C          - KSUP(1) -- IDIM1, dimension of KSEC1
C          - KSUP(2) -- IDIM2, dimension of KSEC2
C          - KSUP(3) -- IDIM3, dimension of KSEC3
C          - KSUP(4) -- IDIM4, dimension of KSEC4
C          - KSUP(5) -- M (number of elements in values
C              first index)
C          - KSUP(6) -- N (number of subsets, second in
C              values array)
C          - KSUP(7) -- JVC (number of elements in CVAL
C          - KSUP(8) -- total bufr message length in by
```



```

C      - KSUP(9) -- IDIM0, dimension of KSEC0
C      *KSEC0* - array containing section 0 information
C      KSEC0(1)-- length of section 0 (bytes)
C      KSEC0(2)-- total length of Bufr message (b
C      KSEC0(3)-- Bufr Edition number
C      *KSEC1* - array containing section 1 information
C      KSEC1(1)-- length of section 1 (bytes)
C      KSEC1(2)-- Bufr Edition number
C      KSEC1(3)-- originating centre
C      KSEC1(4)-- update sequence number
C      KSEC1(5)-- flag (presence of section 2)
C      KSEC1(6)-- bufr message type
C      KSEC1(7)-- bufr message subtype
C      KSEC1(8)-- version number of local table used
C      KSEC1(9)-- century year
C      KSEC1(10)-- month
C      KSEC1(11)-- day
C      KSEC1(12)-- hour
C      KSEC1(13)-- minute
C      KSEC1(14)-- Bufr Master table number
C      KSEC1(15)-- version number of Master table used
C      KSEC1(16) - KSEC1(JSEC1) -- local ADP centre
C      information (BYTE by BYTE)
C      *KSEC2* - array containing section 2 information
C      KSEC2(1)-- length of section 2 (bytes)
C      KSEC2(2) to KSEC2(47) RDB key
C      *KSEC3* - array containing section 3 information
C      KSEC3(1)-- length of section 3 (bytes)
C      KSEC3(2)-- reserved
C      KSEC3(3)-- number of subsets
C      KSEC3(4)-- flag (data type, data compression
C      *KSEC4* - array containing section 4 information
C      KSEC4(1)-- length of section 4 (bytes)
C      KSEC4(2)-- reserved
C      *CNAMES* - character array containing element names
C      *CUNITS* - character array containing units
C      *VALUES* - real array (expanded data values)
C      *CVALS* - character array containing CCITT IA No 5
C      element entries
C      *KERR* - returned error code
C
C
C

```

4.2.2 Printing routines

When observations have been unpacked the various sections can be printed if required, by using the routines below.

CALL BUPRS0 (KSEC0) To print section 0.

CALL BUPRS1 (KSEC1) To print section 1.

CALL BUUKEY(KSEC1, KSEC2, KEY, KSUP, KERR)
This routine (buukey) must be called before calling print routine.

CALL BUPRS2 (KSUP,KEY) To print section 2.

Input:

KSUP - array containing supplementary information

- KSUP(1) -- IDIM1, dimension of KSEC1
- KSUP(2) -- IDIM2, dimension of KSEC2
- KSUP(3) -- IDIM3, dimension of KSEC3
- KSUP(4) -- IDIM4, dimension of KSEC4
- KSUP(5) -- M (number of elements in values first index)
- KSUP(6) -- N (number of subsets, second in values array)
- KSUP(7) -- JVC (number of elements in CVAL)
- KSUP(8) -- total bufr message length in by
- KSUP(9) -- IDIM0, dimension of KSEC0

KEY - array containing section 2 information

- KEY(1)-- length of section 2 (bytes)
- KEY(2)-- RDB type
- KEY(3)-- RDB subtype
- KEY(4)-- year
- KEY(5)-- month
- KEY(6)-- day
- KEY(7)-- hour
- KEY(8)-- minute
- KEY(9)-- second
- KEY(10)-- longitude1
- KEY(11)-- latitude1
- KEY(12)-- longitude2
- KEY(13)-- latitude2
- KEY(14)-- number of subsets
- KEY(15)-- ident (numeric)
- KEY(16)-- ident (CCITTIA5) one character
- KEY(17)-- ident (CCITTIA5) one character
- KEY(18)-- ident (CCITTIA5) one character
- KEY(19)-- ident (CCITTIA5) one character
- KEY(20)-- ident (CCITTIA5) one character
- KEY(21)-- ident (CCITTIA5) one character
- KEY(22)-- ident (CCITTIA5) one character
- KEY(23)-- ident (CCITTIA5) one character
- KEY(24)-- ident (CCITTIA5) one character
- KEY(25)-- total Bufr message length in bytes
- KEY(26)-- day (RDB insertion)
- KEY(27)-- hour (RDB insertion)
- KEY(28)-- minute (RDB insertion)
- KEY(29)-- second (RDB insertion)
- KEY(30)-- day (MDB insertion)


```
C      KEY(31)-- hour (MDB insertion)
C      KEY(32)-- minute (MDB insertion)
C      KEY(33)-- second (MDB insertion)
C      KEY(34)-- correction number
C      KEY(35)-- part
C      KEY(36)-- 0
C      KEY(37)-- correction number
C      KEY(38)-- part
C      KEY(39)-- 0
C      KEY(40)-- correction number
C      KEY(41)-- part
C      KEY(42)-- 0
C      KEY(43)-- correction number
C      KEY(44)-- part
C      KEY(45)-- 0
C      KEY(46)-- the lowest Q/C % confidence
C      The BUSEL routine must be called before printing.
C      CALL BUSEL(KTDLEN, KTDLST, KTDEXL, KTDEXP, KERR)
C      CALL BUPRS3 (KSEC3,KTDLEN,KTDLST,KTDEXL,KTDEXP,KELEM,CNAMES)
C      to print section 3.
C
C      Input:
C      KSEC3  - array containing section 3 information
C      KSEC3(1)-- length of section 3 (bytes)
C      KSEC3(2)-- reserved
C      KSEC3(3)-- number of subsets
C      KSEC3(4)-- flag (data type, data compression
C      KTDLEN  - number of data descriptors in KTDLST
C      KTDLST  - array containing data descriptors in section
C      KTDEXL  - number of entries in list of expanded data
C      descriptors
C      KTDEXP  - array containing expanded data descriptors
C      KELEM   - dimension of CNAMES, CUNITS array
C      CNAMES  - character array containing element names
```


5 OPERATIONAL DAILY ARCHIVE CONTENTS

MARS Operational Daily Archives contain all the data described in section 5.1, 5.2, 5.3 and 5.4. Archiving of different data types started at different times, and content and structure have changed over the years. All this data is archived as version 1, i.e. EXPVER=1 for retrieval (this is the default). As the WMO GRIB Code does not have a missing data indicator, ECMWF have adopted the following convention for storing data that is missing: in Section 4 (Binary Data Section) of the GRIB Code the scale factor and Reference Value have all bits set to one (1). Also, all data values are set to zero. In the routine GRIBEX, which is used to decode WMO GRIB coded data, missing data is indicated by the fact that the number of values decoded is set negative (the data array contains all zeroes).

5.1 Surface Fields

5.1.1 Surface data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Times: 00, 06, 12, 18

- (a) Period: 29/8/82 (1800) - 20/4/83 (1200)
Structure: 1.875 x 1.875 lat/long grid
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D

Missing data:

Snowdepth (141) is actually missing for the entire period.

- (b) Period: 20/4/83 (1800) - 30/4/85 (1800)
Structure: N48, Gaussian grid
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Geopotential (Orography)	129	Z
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V

Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Land sea mask	172	LSM
Surface roughness	173	SR
Albedo	174	AL
Climat. deep soil temperature	183	CDST
Climat. deep soil wetness	184	CDSW

Missing data

Date	Time
26/7/83	18
27/7/83	00
28/7/83	06, 12
19/8/83	06, 12
27/9/83	18
28/9/83	00, 06, 12
2/10/83	06, 12
5/10/83	18
6/10/83	00
1/11/83	06, 12
5/11/83	06, 12, 18
6/11/83	00
8/11/83	18
9/11/83	00, 06, 12
15/12/83	06, 12
17/12/83	06, 12
20/12/83	18
21/12/83	00, 18
22/12/83	00
24/12/83	18
25/12/83	00, 06, 12
27/12/83	06, 12
29/12/83	18
30/12/83	00
14/4/84	18
15/4/84	00, 06, 12
9/8/84	18
10/8/84	00
19/8/84	18
20/8/84	00
28/9/84	06, 12
11/10/84	18
12/10/84	00
25/10/84	06, 12
21/11/84	18
22/11/84	00
15/12/84	06, 12
27/12/84	18

28/12/84 00

23/4/85 06, 12

24/4/85 06, 12

29/4/85 18

30/4/85 00

- (c) Period: 1/5/85 (0000) - 30/6/85 (1800)
 Structure: N80 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters: same as for period 21/4/83 - 30/4/85

Missing data:

<u>Date</u>	<u>Time</u>
13/6/85	18
14/6/85	00, 06, 12

- (d) Period: 1/7/85 (0000) - 14/7/86 (1800)
 Structure: N80 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW

Missing data

8/11/85 06 Missing fields are 128, 151, 170 and 171. These data are in GRIB Edition 0 and were recovered from GETDATA archive

- (e) Period: 15/7/86 (0000) - 6/4/87 (1800)
 Structure: N80 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Geopotential (Orography)	129	Z
Surface pressure	134	SP

Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Land/Sea mask	172	LSM
Surface roughness	173	SR
Albedo	174	AL
Climat. deep soil temperature	183	CDST
Climat. deep soil wetness	184	CDSW
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
E-W orographic variance	190	EWOV
N-S orographic variance	191	NSOV
NW-SE orographic variance	192	NWOV
NE-SW orographic variance	193	NEOV

Missing data: None

- (f) Period: 7/4/87 (0000) - 8/4/91 (1800)
 Structure: N80 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Geopotential (Orography)	129	Z
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Land sea mask	172	LSM
Surface roughness	173	SR

Albedo	174	AL
Climat. deep soil temperature	183	CDST
Climat. deep soil wetness	184	CDSW
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
E-W orographic variance	190	EWOV
N-S orographic variance	191	NSOV
NW-SE orographic variance	192	NWOV
NE-SW orographic variance	193	NEOV
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Percentage of Vegetation	199	VEG
Variance of sub-grid scale orography	200	VSO

Missing data: None

- (g) Period: 9/4/91 (0000) - 16/9/91 (1800)
 Structure: N80 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Geopotential (Orography)	129	Z
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Land sea mask	172	LSM
Surface roughness	173	SR
Albedo	174	AL
Climat. deep soil temperature	183	CDST
Climat. deep soil wetness	184	CDSW
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC

E-W orographic variance	190	EWOV
N-S orographic variance	191	NSOV
NW-SE orographic variance	192	NWOV
NE-SW orographic variance	193	NEOV
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Percentage of Vegetation	199	VEG
Variance of sub-grid scale orography	200	VSO
Precip. analysis weights	204	PAW
Total precipitation	228	TP

Missing data: None

- (h) Period: 17/9/91 (0000) - 03/08/93 (1800)
 Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters: same as for period 09/04/91 - 16/09/91
- (i) Period: 04/8/93 (0000) - 01/03/94 (1800)
 Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Geopotential (Orography)	129	Z
Surface pressure	134	SP
Soil temperature level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness level 1	140	SWL1
Snowdepth	141	SD
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature level 2	170	STL2
Soil wetness level 2	171	SWL2
Land sea mask	172	LSM
Surface roughness	173	SR
Albedo	174	AL
Soil temperature level 3	183	STL3
Soil wetness level 3	184	SWL3
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
E-W orographic variance	190	EWOV

N-S orographic variance	191	NSOV
NW-SE orographic variance	192	NWOV
NE-SW orographic variance	193	NEOV
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Percentage of Vegetation	199	VEG
Variance of sub-grid scale orography	200	VSO
Precip. analysis weights	204	PAW
Total precipitation	228	TP
Apparent Surface Humidity	233	ASQ
Logarithm of surface roughness length for heat.	234	LSRH
Skin Temperature	235	SKT
Soil temperature level 4	236	STL4
Soil wetness level 4	237	SWL4

Missing data: None

- (j) Period: 2/3/94 (0000) - 22/8/94 (1800)
 Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Geopotential (Orography)	129	Z
Surface pressure	134	SP
Soil temperature level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness level 1	140	SWL1
Snowdepth	141	SD
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature level 2	170	STL2
Soil wetness level 2	171	SWL2
Land sea mask	172	LSM
Surface roughness	173	SR
Albedo	174	AL
Soil temperature level 3	183	STL3
Soil wetness level 3	184	SWL3
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC

E-W orographic variance	190	EWOV
N-S orographic variance	191	NSOV
NW-SE orographic variance	192	NWOV
NE-SW orographic variance	193	NEOV
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Percentage of Vegetation	199	VEG
Variance of sub-grid scale orography	200	VSO
Apparent Surface Humidity	233	ASQ
Logarithm of surface roughness length for heat.	234	LSRH
Skin Temperature	235	SKT
Soil temperature level 4	236	STL4
Soil wetness level 4	237	SWL4

Missing data: None

- (k) **Period:** 23/08/94 (0000) - 3/04/95 (1800)
Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Geopotential (Orography)	129	Z
Surface pressure	134	SP
Precipitable water content	137	PWC
Soil temperature level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness level 1	140	SWL1
Snowdepth	141	SD
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature level 2	170	STL2
Soil wetness level 2	171	SWL2
Land sea mask	172	LSM
Surface roughness	173	SR
Albedo	174	AL
Soil temperature level 3	183	STL3

Soil wetness level 3	184	SWL3
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
E-W orographic variance	190	EWOV
N-S orographic variance	191	NSOV
NW-SE orographic variance	192	NWOV
NE-SW orographic variance	193	NEOV
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Percentage of Vegetation	199	VEG
Variance of sub-grid scale orography	200	VSO
Apparent Surface Humidity	233	ASQ
Logarithm of surface roughness length for heat.	234	LSRH
Skin Temperature	235	SKT
Soil temperature level 4	236	STL4
Soil wetness level 4	237	SWL4

Missing data: None

- (l) **Period:** 04/04/95 (0000) - onwards
Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Geopotential (Orography)	129	Z
Surface pressure	134	SP
Total Column Water	136	TCW
Total Column Water Vapour	137	TCWV
Soil temperature level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness level 1	140	SWL1
Snowdepth	141	SD
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Standard Deviation of Orography	160	SDOR
Anisotropy of Subgrid Scale Orography	161	ISOR
Angle of Subgrid Scale Orography	162	ANOR
Slope of Subgrid Scale Orography	163	SLOR
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U

Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature level 2	170	STL2
Soil wetness level 2	171	SWL2
Land sea mask	172	LSM
Surface roughness	173	SR
Albedo	174	AL
Soil temperature level 3	183	STL3
Soil wetness level 3	184	SWL3
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Percentage of Vegetation	199	VEG
Apparent Surface Humidity	233	ASQ
Logarithm of surface roughness length for heat.	234	LSRH
Skin Temperature	235	SKT
Soil temperature level 4	236	STL4
Soil wetness level 4	237	SWL4

Missing data: None

5.1.2 Surface data - Initialised analysis

Times: 00, 06, 12, 18

- (a) Period: 30/9/79 (1800) - 30/11/80 (1200)
 Structure: 1.875 x 1.875 lat/long grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD

Missing data:

Surface soil wetness (140) is missing from 1800 on 30/9/79 until 1200 on 2/11/80 inclusive.

- (b) Period: 30/11/80 (1800) - 20/4/83 (1200)
 Structure: 1.875 x 1.875 lat/long grid

Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D

Missing data:

Snowdepth (141) is missing from 1800 19/4/82 to 20/4/83.

- (c) **Period:** 20/4/83 (1800) - 30/4/85 (1800)
Structure: N48 Gaussian Grid
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW

Missing data:

Same dates and times as for uninitialised analysis.

- (d) **Period:** 1/5/85 (0000) - 14/7/86 (1800)
Structure: N80 Gaussian Grid
Parameters: Same as for period 20/4/83 - 30/4/85

Missing data:

13/6/85 18
14/6/85 00,06,12

- (e) **Period:** 15/7/86 (0000) - 6/4/87 (1800)

Structure: N80 Gaussian Grid

Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC

Missing data: None

(f) Period: 7/4/87 (0000) - 8/4/91 (1800)

Structure: N80 Gaussian Grid

Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC

High cloud cover 188 HCC
 Skin reservoir content 198 SRC

Missing data: None

(g) Period: 9/4/91 (0000) -16/9/91 (1800)
 Structure: N80 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Albedo	174	AL
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC

Missing data: None

(h) Period: 17/9/91 (0000) - 03/08/93 (1800)
 Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters: Same as for period 9/4/91-16/9/91

Missing data: None

(i) Period: 04/08/93 (0000) - 01/03/94 (1800)
 Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV

Surface pressure	134	SP
Soil temperature level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness level 1	140	SWL1
Snowdepth	141	SD
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature level 2	170	STL2
Soil wetness level 2	171	SWL2
Albedo	174	AL
Soil temperature level 3	183	STL3
Soil wetness level 3	184	SWL3
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Apparent Surface Humidity	233	ASQ
Skin Temperature	235	SKT
Soil temperature level 4	236	STL4
Soil wetness level 4	237	SWL4

Missing data: None

- (j) Period: 02/03/94 (0000) - 22/08/94 (1800)
- Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
- Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Soil temperature level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness level 1	140	SWL1
Snowdepth	141	SD
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature level 2	170	STL2
Soil wetness level 2	171	SWL2
Soil temperature level 3	183	STL3
Soil wetness level 3	184	SWL3

Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Apparent Surface Humidity	233	ASQ
Skin Temperature	235	SKT
Soil temperature level 4	236	STL4
Soil wetness level 4	237	SWL4
Forecast albedo	243	FAL
Forecast surface roughness	244	FSR
Forecast log surface roughness	245	FLSR

Missing data: None

- (k) Period: 23/08/94 (0000) - 03/04/95 (1800)
Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Precipitable water content	137	PWC
Soil temperature level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness level 1	140	SWL1
Snowdepth	141	SD
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature level 2	170	STL2
Soil wetness level 2	171	SWL2
Soil temperature level 3	183	STL3
Soil wetness level 3	184	SWL3
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Apparent Surface Humidity	233	ASQ
Skin Temperature	235	SKT
Soil temperature level 4	236	STL4
Soil wetness level 4	237	SWL4
Forecast albedo	243	FAL
Forecast surface roughness	244	FSR
Forecast log surface roughness	245	FLSR

Missing data: None

- (l) **Period:** 04/04/95 (0000) - onwards
Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Total Column Water	136	TCW
Total Column Water Vapour	137	TCWV
Soil temperature level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness level 1	140	SWL1
Snowdepth	141	SD
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature level 2	170	STL2
Soil wetness level 2	171	SWL2
Soil temperature level 3	183	STL3
Soil wetness level 3	184	SWL3
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Apparent Surface Humidity	233	ASQ
Skin Temperature	235	SKT
Soil temperature level 4	236	STL4
Soil wetness level 4	237	SWL4
Forecast albedo	243	FAL
Forecast surface roughness	244	FSR
Forecast log surface roughness	245	FLSR

Missing data: None

5.1.3 Surface data - First Guess

- (a) **Period:** 29/8/82 (1800) - 20/4/83 (1200)
Times: 00, 06, 12, 18
Steps: 06
Structure: 1.875 x 1.875 lat/long grid

Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Surface stress	148	SS
Surface net radiation	149	SNR
Top net radiation	150	TNR
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D

(b) Period: 20/4/83 (1800) - 30/4/85 (1800)

Times: 00, 06, 12, 18

Steps: 06

Structure: N48, Gaussian Grid

Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Surface roughness	173	SR
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR

E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E

Missing data:

Date	Time
26/7/83	18
27/7/83	00, 06
28/7/83	12, 18
19/8/83	12, 18
28/9/83	00, 06, 12, 18
2/10/83	12, 18
6/10/83	00, 06
1/11/83	12, 18
6/11/83	00, 06
9/11/83	00, 06, 12, 18
15/12/83	12, 18
17/12/83	12, 18
21/12/83	00, 06
22/12/83	00, 06
25/12/83	00, 06, 12, 18
27/12/83	12, 18
30/12/83	00, 06
15/4/84	00, 06, 12, 18
10/8/84	00, 06
20/8/84	00, 06
28/9/84	12, 18
12/10/84	00, 06
25/10/84	12, 18
22/11/84	00, 06
15/12/84	12, 18
28/12/84	00, 06
23/4/85	12, 18
24/4/85	12, 18
30/4/85	00, 06

- (c) Period: 1/5/85 (0000) - 14/7/86 (1800)
 Times: 00, 06, 12, 18
 Steps: 06
 Structure: N80 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters: Same as for period 20/4/83 - 30/4/85

Missing data:

Date	Time	
14/6/86	00	missing fields are 128,151,170,171,173 These data are in GRIB edition 0 and were recovered from GETDATA

14/6/85 00, 06, 12, 18
 8/11/85 06 missing fields are 128,151,170,171,173,182
 These data are in GRIB edition 0 and were recovered from GETDATA archive.

(d) Period: 15/7/86 (0000) - 6/4/87 (1800)
 Times: 00, 06, 12, 18
 Steps: 06
 Structure: N80 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Surface roughness	173	SR
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD

Missing data: None

(e) Period: 7/4/87 (0000) - 11/2/91 (1800)

Times: 00, 06, 12, 18
 Steps: 06
 Structure: N80 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Surface roughness	173	SR
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Max. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	201	MX2T
Min. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	202	MN2T
<u>Missing data:</u> None		

(f) Period: 11/2/91 (2100) - 8/4/91 (1800)
 Times: 00, 03, 06, 09, 12, 15, 18, 21
 Steps: H+6 for 00, 06, 12, 18
 H+3 for 03, 09, 15, 21
 H+9 for 03, 09, 15, 21
 Structure: N80 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters: as for period 7/4/87 - 11/2/91

Missing data: None

(g) Period: 8/4/91 (2100) - 16/9/91 (1800)
 Times: 00, 03, 06, 09, 12, 15, 18, 21
 Steps: H+6 for 00, 06, 12, 18
 H+3 for 03, 09, 15, 21
 H+9 for 03, 09, 15, 21
 Structure: N80 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Surface roughness	173	SR
Albedo	174	A
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC

Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Max. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	201	MX2T
Min. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	202	MN2T
Runoff	205	RO

Missing data: None

(h) **Period:** 16/9/91 (2100) - 03/08/93 (1800)
Times: 00, 03, 06, 09, 12, 15, 18, 21
Steps: H+6 for 00, 06, 12, 18
H+3 for 03, 09, 15, 21
H+9 for 03, 09, 15, 21
Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
Parameters: Same as for period 8/9/91-16/9/91

(i) **Period:** 04/08/93 (2100) - 01/03/94 (1800)
Times: 00, 03, 06, 09, 12, 15, 18, 21
Steps: H+6 for 00, 06, 12, 18
H+3 for 03, 09, 15, 21
H+9 for 03, 09, 15, 21
Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Soil temperature level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness level 1	140	SWL1
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature level 2	170	STL2

Soil wetness level 2	171	SWL2
Surface roughness	173	SR
Albedo	174	A
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Climatological deep soil temperature	183	STL3
Climatological deep soil wetness	184	SWL3
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Max. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	201	MX2T
Min. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	202	MN2T
Runoff	205	RO
Apparent Surface Humidity	233	ASQ
Skin Temperature	235	SKT
Soil temperature level 4	236	STL4
Soil wetness level 4	237	SWL4

Missing data: None

- (j) Period: 02/03/94 (0000) - 03/04/95 (1800)
 Times: 00, 03, 06, 09, 12, 15, 18, 21
 Steps: H+6 for 00, 06, 12, 18
 H+3 for 03, 09, 15, 21
 H+9 for 03, 09, 15, 21
 Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Soil temperature level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness level 1	140	SWL1
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP

Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature level 2	170	STL2
Soil wetness level 2	171	SWL2
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Climatological deep soil temperature	183	STL3
Climatological deep soil wetness	184	SWL3
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Max. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	201	MX2T
Min. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	202	MN2T
Runoff	205	RO
Apparent Surface Humidity	233	ASQ
Skin Temperature	235	SKT
Soil temperature level 4	236	STL4
Soil wetness level 4	237	SWL4
Forecast Albedo	243	FAL
Forecast surface roughness	244	FSR
Forecast logarithm of surface roughness for heat	245	FLSR

Missing data: None

- (k) Period: 04/04/95 (0000) - onwards
 Times: 00, 03, 06, 09, 12, 15, 18, 21
 Steps: H+6 for 00, 06, 12, 18
 H+3 for 03, 09, 15, 21

H+9 for 03, 09, 15, 21

Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Total Column Water	136	TCW
Total Column Water Vapour	137	TCWV
Soil temperature level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness level 1	140	SWL1
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature level 2	170	STL2
Soil wetness level 2	171	SWL2
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Climatological deep soil temperature	183	STL3
Climatological deep soil wetness	184	SWL3
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Max. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	201	MX2T
Min. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	202	MN2T
Runoff	205	RO
Apparent Surface Humidity	233	ASQ
Skin Temperature	235	SKT
Soil temperature level 4	236	STL4

Soil wetness level 4	237	SWL4
Forecast Albedo	243	FAL
Forecast surface roughness	244	FSR
Forecast logarithm of surface roughness for heat	245	FLSR

Missing data: None

5.1.4 Surface data - Forecast

Time: 12

- (a) Period: 1/7/85 - 14/7/86
 Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: N80, Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Surface roughness	173	SR
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E

- (b) Period: 15/7/86 - 6/4/87
 Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: N80, Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Surface roughness	173	SR
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD

- (c) Period: 7/4/87 - 14/11/90
 Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: N80, Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF

Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Surface roughness	173	SR
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Max. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	201	MX2T
Min. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	202	MN2T
(d) Period:	15/11/90 - 8/4/91	
Step:	3-hourly to HH+12, then 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240	
Structure:	N80, Gaussian Grid	
Parameters:	Same as for the period 7/4/87 - 14/11/90	
(e) Period:	9/4/91 - 16/9/91	
Step:	3-hourly to HH+12, then 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240	
Structure:	N80, Gaussian Grid	
Parameters:		
	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW

Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHf
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Surface roughness	173	SR
Albedo	174	AL
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Max. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	201	MX2T
Min. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	202	MN2T
Runoff	205	RO

- (f) Period: 17/9/91 - 03/08/93
 Step: 3-hourly to HH+12, then 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW

Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Surface roughness	173	SR
Albedo	174	AL
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Max. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	201	MX2T
Min. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	202	MN2T
Runoff	205	RO

- (g) Period: 04/08/93 - 01/03/94
 Step: 3-hourly to HH+12, then 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Soil temperature level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness level 1	140	SWL1

Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature level 2	170	STL2
Soil wetness level 2	171	SWL2
Surface roughness	173	SR
Albedo	174	AL
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Climatological deep soil temperature	183	STL3
Climatological deep soil wetness	184	SWL3
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Max. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	201	MX2T
Min. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	202	MN2T
Runoff	205	RO
Apparent Surface Humidity	233	ASQ
Skin Temperature	235	SKT
Soil Temperature level 4	236	STL4
Soil Wetness level 4	237	SWL4

- (h) Period: 02/03/94 - 22/08/94
 Step: 3-hourly to HH+12, then 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV

Surface pressure	134	SP
Soil temperature level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness level 1	140	SWL1
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHf
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature level 2	170	STL2
Soil wetness level 2	171	SWL2
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Climatological deep soil temperature	183	STL3
Climatological deep soil wetness	184	SWL3
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Max. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	201	MX2T
Min. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	202	MN2T
Runoff	205	RO
Apparent Surface Humidity	233	ASQ
Skin Temperature	235	SKT
Soil Temperature level 4	236	STL4
Soil Wetness level 4	237	SWL4
Forecast Albedo	243	FAL
Forecast surface roughness	244	FSR
Forecast logarithm of surface roughness for heat.	245	FLSR

(i) Period: 23/08/94 - 03/04/95

Step: 3-hourly to HH+12, then 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Precipitable water content	137	PWC
Soil temperature level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness level 1	140	SWL1
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature level 2	170	STL2
Soil wetness level 2	171	SWL2
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Climatological deep soil temperature	183	STL3
Climatological deep soil wetness	184	SWL3
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Max. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	201	MX2T
Min. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	202	MN2T
Runoff	205	RO
Apparent Surface Humidity	233	ASQ
Skin Temperature	235	SKT
Soil Temperature level 4	236	STL4

Soil Wetness level 4	237	SWL4
Forecast Albedo	243	FAL
Forecast surface roughness	244	FSR
Forecast logarithm of surface roughness for heat.	245	FLSR

- (j) Period: 04/04/95 - onwards
 Step: 3-hourly to HH+12, then 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Budget values	128	BV
Surface pressure	134	SP
Total Column Water	136	TCW
Total Column Water Vapour	137	TCWV
Soil temperature level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness level 1	140	SWL1
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature level 2	170	STL2
Soil wetness level 2	171	SWL2
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Climatological deep soil temperature	183	STL3
Climatological deep soil wetness	184	SWL3
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC

Max. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	201	MX2T
Min. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	202	MN2T
Runoff	205	RO
Apparent Surface Humidity	233	ASQ
Skin Temperature	235	SKT
Soil Temperature level 4	236	STL4
Soil Wetness level 4	237	SWL4
Forecast Albedo	243	FAL
Forecast surface roughness	244	FSR
Forecast logarithm of surface roughness for heat.	245	FLSR

5.2 Model Level Fields

5.2.1 Model level data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Times: 00, 06, 12, 18

- (a) Period: 20/4/83 (1800) - 30/4/85 (1800)
 Structure: T63 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 16
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

Missing data: Same dates and times as uninitialised surface data.

- (b) Period: 1/5/85 (0000) - 3/3/86 (1800)
 Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 16
 Parameters: Same as for period 20/4/83 - 30/4/85

Missing data: None.

- (c) Period: 4/3/86 (0000) - 12/5/86 (1800)
 Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 16
 Parameters: Same as for period 20/4/83 - 30/4/85 plus

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Atmospheric tide	127	AT

- (d) Period: 13/5/86 (0000) - 12/4/87 (1800)

Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 19
 Parameters: Same as for period 4/3/86 to 12/5/86

- (e) Period: 3/4/87 (0000) - 16/9/91 (1800)
 Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 19
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Atmospheric tide	127	AT
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

- (f) Period: 17/9/91 (0000) - 22/08/94 (1800)
 Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 31
 Parameters: same as for period 13/4/87 - 16/9/91

- (g) Period: 23/08/94 (0000) - 03/04/95 (1800)
 Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 31
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Atmospheric tide	127	AT
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Orography (spectral)	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

- (h) Period: 04/04/95 (0000) - onwards
 Levels: 1 to 31

Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Atmospheric tide	127	AT
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Orography (spectral)	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

Structure: Quasi-regular (reduced) N160 Gaussian Grid

Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Specific humidity	133	Q

5.2.2 Model level data - Initialised analysis

Times: 00, 06, 12, 18

(a) Period: 20/4/83 (1800) - 30/4/85 (1800)

Structure: T63 Spherical Harmonics

Levels: 1 to 16

Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

Missing data: Same dates and times as initialised surface data.

(b) Period: 1/5/85 (0000) - 12/5/86 (1800)

Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics

Levels: 1 to 16

Parameters: Same as for period 20/4/83 - 30/4/85

Missing data: LNSP for 00 and 12 on 14/6/85.

(c) Period: 13/5/86 (0000) - 12/4/87 (1800)

Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics

Levels: 1 to 19

Parameters: Same as for period 20/4/83 - 30/4/85

(d) Period: 13/4/87 - 16/9/91 (1800)

Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics

Levels: 1 to 19

Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

(e) Period: 17/9/91 (0000) - 03/04/95 (1800)
 Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 31
 Parameters: Same as for period 13/4/87 - 16/9/91

(f) Period: 04/04/95 (0000) - onwards
 Levels: 1 to 31

Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

Structure: Quasi-regular (reduced) N160 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Specific humidity	133	Q
Cloud Liquid Water Content	246	CLWC
Cloud Ice Water Content	247	CIWC
Cloud Cover	248	CC

5.2.3 Model level data - First Guess

(a) Period: 20/4/83 (1800) - 30/4/85 (1800)
 Times: 00, 06, 12, 18
 Steps: 06
 Structure: T63 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 16
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

Missing data: Same dates and times as first guess surface data.

(b) Period: 1/5/85 (0000) - 12/5/86 (1800)
 Times: 00, 06, 12, 18
 Steps: 06
 Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 16
 Parameters: Same as for period 20/4/83 - 30/4/85

Missing data: Same dates and times as first guess surface data.

(c) **Period:** 13/5/86 (0000) - 12/4/87 (1800)
Times: 00, 06, 12, 18
Steps: 06
Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
Levels: 1 to 19
Parameters: Same as for period 20/4/83 - 30/4/85

(d) **Period:** 13/4/87 (0000) - 11/2/91 (1800)
Times: 00, 06, 12, 18
Steps: 06
Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
Levels: 1 to 19
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

(e) **Period:** 11/2/91 (2100) - 16/9/91(1800)
Times: 00, 03, 06, 09, 12, 15, 18, 21
Steps: H+6 for 00, 06, 12, 18
H+3 for 03, 09, 15, 21
H+9 for 03, 09, 15, 21
Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
Levels: 1 to 19
Parameters: Same as for period 13/4/87 - 11/2/91

(f) **Period:** 16/9/91 (2100) - 03/04/95 (1800)
Times: 00, 03, 06, 09, 12, 15, 18, 21
Steps: H+6 for 00, 06, 12, 18
H+3 for 03, 09, 15, 21
H+9 for 03, 09, 15, 21
Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
Levels: 1 to 31
Parameters: Same as for period 13/4/87 - 11/2/91

(g) **Period:** 03/04/95 (2100) - onwards
Times: 00, 03, 06, 09, 12, 15, 18, 21
Steps: H+6 for 00, 06, 12, 18
H+3 for 03, 09, 15, 21
H+9 for 03, 09, 15, 21

Levels: 1 to 31

Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics

Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

Structure: Quasi-regular (reduced) N160 Gaussian Grid

Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Specific humidity	133	Q
Cloud Liquid Water Content	246	CLWC
Cloud Ice Water Content	247	CIWC
Cloud Cover	248	CC

5.2.4 Model level data - Forecast

Time: 12

- (a) Period: 1/7/85 - 12/5/86
 Steps: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: T106, Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 16
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

- (b) Period: 13/5/86 - 12/4/87
 Steps: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: T106, Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 19
 Parameters: Same as for period 1/7/85 - 12/5/86

- (c) Period: 13/4/87 - 14/11/90
 Steps: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: T106, Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 19
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

(d) Period: 15/11/90 - 16/9/91
 Steps: 3-hourly to HH+12, then 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: T106, Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 19
 Parameters: Same as for period 13/4/87 - 14/11/90

(e) Period: 17/9/91 - 03/04/95
 Steps: 3-hourly to HH+12, then 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 31
 Parameters: Same as for period 13/4/87 to 14/11/90

(f) Period: 04/04/95 - onwards
 Steps: 3-hourly to HH+12, then 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Levels: 1 to 31

Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

Structure: Quasi-regular (reduced) N160 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Specific humidity	133	Q
Cloud Liquid Water Content	246	CLWC
Cloud Ice Water Content	247	CIWC
Cloud Cover	248	CC

5.3 Pressure level fields

5.3.1 Pressure level data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Times: 00, 06, 12, 18

- (a) Period: 29/8/82 (1800) - 20/4/83 (1200)
- Structure: T63 Spherical Harmonics
- Levels: 13-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30
- Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D
Relative humidity	157	R

- (b) Period: 20/4/83 (1800) - 30/5/85 (1800)
- Structure: T63 Spherical Harmonics
- Levels: 14-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
- Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D
Relative humidity	157	R

Missing data: Same dates and times as for uninitialised data.

- (c) Period: 1/5/85 (0000) 16/9/91 (1800)
- Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
- Levels: 14-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
- Parameters: Same as for period 20/4/83 - 30/5/85

Missing data:

13/6/85 18

Data from 00,06,12 on 14/6/85 is in the Experimental Edition of the GRIB code.

- (d) Period: 17/9/91 (0000) - 9/12/91 (1800)
- Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
- Levels: 14-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
- Parameters: Same as for period 20/4/83 - 30/5/85

- (e) **Period:** 10/12/91 (0000) - 03/04/95 (1800)
Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
Levels: 15-1000, 925, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D
Relative humidity	157	R

- (f) **Period:** 04/04/95 (0000) - onwards
Levels: 15-1000, 925, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10

Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D
Relative humidity	157	R

Structure: Quasi-regular (reduced) N160 Gaussian Grid
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Specific humidity	133	Q

5.3.2 Pressure level data - Initialised analysis

Times: 00, 06, 12, 18

- (a) **Period:** 30/9/79 (1800) - 19/4/82 (1200)
Structure: T63 Spherical Harmonics
Levels: 13-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T

u velocity	131	U
v velocity	132	V
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W

Missing data: The 70 hPa level is missing from 1800 on 30/9/79 to 1200 on 14/4/80 inclusive. Data for 1800 on 13/3/80 is also missing.

Times: 00, 06, 12, 18

- (b) **Period:** 19/4/82 (1800) - 20/4/83 (1200)
Structure: T63 Spherical Harmonics
Levels: 13-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D
Relative humidity	157	R

- (c) **Period:** 20/4/83 (1800) - 30/4/85 (1800)
Structure: T63 Spherical Harmonics
Levels: 14-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D
Relative humidity	157	R

Missing data: Same dates and times as for initialised surface analysis.

- (d) **Period:** 1/5/85 (0000) 16/9/91 (1800)
Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
Levels: 14-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
Parameters: Same as for period 21/4/83 - 30/4/85

Missing data:

13/6/85 18
 14/6/85 06
 14/6/85 00, 12 are in Experimental Edition of GRIB code

- (e) **Period:** 17/9/91 (0000) 9/12/91 (1800)
Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics

Levels: 14-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
Parameters: Same as for period 21/4/83 - 30/4/85

(f) Period: 10/12/91 (0000) - 03/04/95 (1800)
Levels: 15-1000, 925, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10

Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D
Relative humidity	157	R

(g) Period: 04/04/95 (0000) onwards
Levels: 15-1000, 925, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10

Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D
Relative humidity	157	R

Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Specific humidity	133	Q

5.3.3 Pressure level data - First Guess

(a) Period: 29/8/82 (1800) - 20/4/83 (1200)
Times: 00, 06, 12, 18
Steps: 06
Structure: T63 Spherical Harmonics
Levels: 13-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO

Divergence 155 D
 Relative humidity 157 R

- (b) Period: 20/4/83 (1800) - 30/4/85 (1800)
 Times: 00, 06, 12, 18
 Steps: 06
 Structure: T63 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 14-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D
Relative humidity	157	R

Missing data: Same dates and times as surface first guess.

- (c) Period: 1/5/85 (0000) - 16/9/91 (1800)
 Times: 00, 06, 12, 18
 Steps: 06
 Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 14-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
 Parameters: Same as for period 20/4/83 - 30/4/85

Missing data:

14/6/85 00, 12
 14/6/85 00, 12 are in Experimental Edition of GRIB code

- (d) Period: 17/9/91 (0000) - 9/12/91 (1800)
 Times: 00, 06, 12, 18
 Steps: 06
 Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 14-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
 Parameters: Same as for period 20/4/83 - 30/4/85

- (e) Period: 10/12/91(0000) - 03/04/95 (1800)
 Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 15-1000, 925, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
 Parameters: Same as for period 20/4/83 - 30/4/85

- (f) Period: 04/04/95 (0000) - onwards
 Levels: 15-1000, 925, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10

Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
--	-------------------	---------------------

Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D
Relative humidity	157	R

Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid

Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Specific humidity	133	Q

5.3.4 Pressure level data - Forecast

Time: 12

- (a) Period: 1/7/85 - 14/11/90
 Steps: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 14-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D
Relative humidity	157	R

- (b) Period: 15/11/90 - 16/9/91
 Steps: 3-hourly to HH+12, then 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 14-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
 Parameters: Same as for period 1/7/85 - 14/11/90

- (c) Period: 17/9/91 - 9/12/91
 Steps: 3-hourly to HH+12, then 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 14-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
 Parameters: Same as for period 1/7/85 - 14/11/90

- (d) Period: 10/12/91 - 03/04/95
 Steps: 3-hourly to HH+12, then 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 15-1000, 925, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
 Parameters: Same as for period 1/7/85 - 14/11/90

- (e) **Period:** 04/04/95 - onwards
Levels: 15-1000, 925, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
Steps: 3-hourly to HH+12, then 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240

Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D
Relative humidity	157	R

Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Specific humidity	133	Q

5.3.5 Pressure level data - Errors in analysis

Time: 00, 06, 12, 18

- (a) **Period:** 20/4/83 (1800) - 30/4/83 (1200)
Structure: 6.0 x 6.0 latitude/longitude grid, global fields
Levels: 7-1000, 500, 300, 200, 100, 50, 10
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
u velocity	131	U
v velocity	132	V
Height (geopotential)	156	GH

- (b) **Period:** 1/3/88 (0000) onwards
Structure: 6.0 x 6.0 latitude/longitude grid, global fields
Levels: 7-1000, 500, 300, 200, 100, 50, 10
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
u velocity	131	U
v velocity	132	V
Height (geopotential)	156	GH

5.3.6 Pressure level data - Errors in first guess

Time: 00, 06, 12, 18

- (a) **Period:** 10/12/91 (0000) - 22/6/92 (1800)
Structure: 6.0 x 6.0 latitude/longitude grid, global fields

Levels: 7-1000, 500, 300, 200, 100, 50, 10

Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
u velocity	131	U
v velocity	132	V
Height (geopotential)	156	GH

- (b) Period: 23/6/92 (0000) onwards
Structure: 6.0 x 6.0 latitude/longitude grid, global fields
Levels: 7-1000, 500, 300, 200, 100, 50, 10
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Temperature	130	T
u velocity	131	U
v velocity	132	V
Height (geopotential)	156	GH

5.4 Observations

Period: 01/09/79 onwards
Structure: WMO FM-94 BUFR Code
Contents:

- Land surface data
- Sea surface data
- Vertical soundings (not satellite)
- Vertical soundings (satellite)
- Single level upper-air (not satellite)
- Single level upper-air (satellite)
- Oceanographic data

See section 7.2 for details of subtypes, subtype numbers and abbreviations.

6 OPERATIONAL MONTHLY MEANS ARCHIVES

MARS monthly means archives contain all the data described in sections 6.1, 6.2 and 6.3. All this data is archived as version 1, i.e. EXPVER=1 for retrieval (this is the default). The major difference of a monthly request from the daily one is that the DAY part of MARS DATE parameter will always be 00. This implies that ranges of dates for monthly means are not allowed. e.g. retrieve, date=930100, stream=monthly, type=forecast, step=12, ...

An important part of a Monthly Means request is that forecast means are for the verification month. In the example above the data would start on 921231 and end on 930131. This is indicated in Section 1 of the GRIB header where the date given is that of the first item in the average which would be 921231 for the above example.

6.1 Surface Fields

6.1.1 Surface data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Times: 00, 06, 12, 18

- (a) Period: 7/85 (0000) - 6/86 (1800)
 Structure: N80 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW

Exception conditions

11/85 06 Fields 151, 170 and 171 have one missing data item. This is indicated in the GRIB header.

- (b) Period: 7/86 (0000) - 9/91 (1800)
 Structure: N80 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD

Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Albedo	174	AL

Exception conditions

7/86 ALL The new field 174 was added on 15/7/86 so all analysis means for that field are for 17 days.

9/91 ALL The model resolution changed to a Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid on 17/9/91, but the monthly means are calculated on an N80 grid for conformity with the data from the start of the month.

- (c) Period: 10/91 (0000) - 7/93 (1800)
- Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
- Parameters: same as for period 7/86 - 9/91

Exception conditions: None

- (d) Period: 8/93 (0000) - 3/95 (1800)
- Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
- Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Surface pressure	134	SP
Soil temperature, level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness, level 1	140	SWL1
Snowdepth	141	SD
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature, level 2	170	STL2
Soil wetness, level 2	171	SWL2
Albedo	174	AL
Soil temperature, level 3	183	STL3
Soil wetness, level 3	184	SWL3
Apparent surface humidity	233	ASQ
Skin temperature	235	SKT
Soil temperature, level 4	236	STL4
Soil wetness, level 4	237	SWL4

Exception conditions

8/93 ALL The new fields 139, 140, 170, 171, 183, 184, 233, 235, 236 and 237 were added on 4/8/93 so all analysis means for those fields are for 28 days. Note that the fields 139, 140, 170 and 171 have changed definition so the values for the first 3 days of the month were not included in the means.

- (e) Period: 4/95 (0000) onward
 Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid (Increased the number of points along latitude rows.)
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Surface pressure	134	SP
Total Column Water	136	TCW
Total Column Water Vapour	137	TCWV
Soil temperature, level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness, level 1	140	SWL1
Snowdepth	141	SD
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature, level 2	170	STL2
Soil wetness, level 2	171	SWL2
Albedo	174	AL
Soil temperature, level 3	183	STL3
Soil wetness, level 3	184	SWL3
Apparent surface humidity	233	ASQ
Skin temperature	235	SKT
Soil temperature, level 4	236	STL4
Soil wetness, level 4	237	SWL4

Exception conditions

4/95 ALL Means for all fields start on 5/4/95 and are for 26 days.

6.1.2 Surface data - Initialised analysis

Monthly means are not calculated for Surface data - Initialised analysis

6.1.3 Surface data - First Guess

Monthly means are not calculated for Surface data - First Guess

6.1.4 Surface data - Forecast

Time: 12

- (a) Period: 8/85 - 6/86
 Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: N80 Gaussian Grid

Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Surface roughness	173	SR
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E

Exception conditions: None

- (b) Period: 7/86 - 3/87
 Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: N80 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V

Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Surface roughness	173	SR
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD

Exception conditions

7/86 ALL The new fields 185, 186, 187, 188, 195, 196 and 197 were added on 15/7/86, so the forecast means for those fields are for 17 days at STEP=006 down to 7 days at STEP=240.

- (c) Period: 4/87 - 3/91
 Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: N80 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Surface roughness	173	SR
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR

Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Max. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	201	MX2T
Min. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	202	MN2T

Exception conditions

4/87 ALL The new fields 198, 201 and 202 were added on 7/4/87, so the forecast means for those fields are for 24 days at STEP=006 down to 14 days at STEP=240.

- (d) Period: 4/91 - 9/91
 Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: N80 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Deep soil temperature	170	DST
Deep soil wetness	171	DSW
Surface roughness	173	SR
Albedo	174	AL
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR

Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Max. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	201	MX2T
Min. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	202	MN2T
Runoff	205	RO

Exception conditions

4/91 ALL The new fields 174 and 205 were added on 9/4/91, so the forecast means for those fields are for 22 days at STEP=006 down to 12 days at STEP=240.

9/91 ALL The model resolution changed to a Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid on 17/9/91, but the monthly means are calculated on an N80 grid for conformity with the data from the start of the month.

- (e) Period: 10/91 - 7/93
 Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters: same as for period 4/91 - 9/91

Exception conditions: None

- (f) Period: 8/93 - 2/94
 Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Surface pressure	134	SP
Soil temperature, level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness, level 1	140	SWL1
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD

Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature, level 2	170	STL2
Soil wetness, level 2	171	SWL2
Surface roughness	173	SR
Albedo	174	AL
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Soil temperature, level 3	183	STL3
Soil wetness, level 3	184	SWL3
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Max. temperature at 2m	201	MX2T
since previous post-processing		
Min. temperature at 2m	202	MN2T
since previous post-processing		
Runoff	205	RO
Apparent surface humidity	233	ASQ
Skin temperature	235	SKT
Soil temperature, level 4	236	STL4
Soil wetness, level 4	237	SWL4

Exception conditions

8/93 ALL The new fields 139, 140, 170, 171, 183, 184, 233, 235, 236 and 237 were added on 4/8/93, so the forecast means for those fields are for 28 days at STEP=006 down to 18 days at STEP=240. Note that the fields 139, 140 170 and 171 have changed definition so the values for days before day 4 of the month were not included in the means.

- (g) Period: 3/94 - 8/94
- Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
- Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
- Parameters:

Field Code MARS Abbrev.

Surface pressure	134	SP
Soil temperature, level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness, level 1	140	SWL1
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature, level 2	170	STL2
Soil wetness, level 2	171	SWL2
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Soil temperature, level 3	183	STL3
Soil wetness, level 3	184	SWL3
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Max. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	201	MX2T
Min. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	202	MN2T
Runoff	205	RO
Apparent surface humidity	233	ASQ
Skin temperature	235	SKT
Soil temperature, level 4	236	STL4
Soil wetness, level 4	237	SWL4
Forecast albedo	243	FAL
Forecast surface roughness	244	FSR
Forecast log surface roughness	245	FLSR

Exception conditions

3/94 ALL The new fields 243, 244 and 245 were added on 2/3/94, so the forecast means for those fields are for 30 days at STEP=006 down to 20 days at STEP=240.

- (h) Period: 9/94 - 3/95
 Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Surface pressure	134	SP
Precipitable Water Content	137	PWC
Soil temperature, level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness, level 1	140	SWL1
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature, level 2	170	STL2
Soil wetness, level 2	171	SWL2
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Soil temperature, level 3	183	STL3
Soil wetness, level 3	184	SWL3
Convective cloud cover	185	CCC
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD
Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Max. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	201	MX2T
Min. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	202	MN2T
Runoff	205	RO
Apparent surface humidity	233	ASQ
Skin temperature	235	SKT
Soil temperature, level 4	236	STL4
Soil wetness, level 4	237	SWL4

Forecast albedo	243	FAL
Forecast surface roughness	244	FSR
Forecast log surface roughness	245	FLSR

Exception conditions

9/94 ALL The new field 137 was added on 23/8/94, so the forecast means for this field is for 30 days at STEP=006 to 192 down to 28 days at STEP=240.

- (i) Period: 4/95 onward
 Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: Quasi-regular N160 Gaussian Grid (Increased the number of points along latitude rows.)
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Surface pressure	134	SP
Total Column Water	136	TCW
Total Column Water Vapour	137	TCWV
Soil temperature, level 1	139	STL1
Soil wetness, level 1	140	SWL1
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Soil temperature, level 2	170	STL2
Soil wetness, level 2	171	SWL2
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
E-W surface stress	180	EWSS
N-S surface stress	181	NSSS
Evaporation	182	E
Soil temperature, level 3	183	STL3
Soil wetness, level 3	184	SWL3
Low cloud cover	186	LCC
Medium cloud cover	187	MCC
High cloud cover	188	HCC
Latitudinal gravity wave stress	195	LGWS
Meridional gravity wave stress	196	MGWS
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD

Skin reservoir content	198	SRC
Max. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	201	MX2T
Min. temperature at 2m since previous post-processing	202	MN2T
Runoff	205	RO
Apparent surface humidity	233	ASQ
Skin temperature	235	SKT
Soil temperature, level 4	236	STL4
Soil wetness, level 4	237	SWL4
Forecast albedo	243	FAL
Forecast surface roughness	244	FSR
Forecast log surface roughness	245	FLSR

Exception conditions

9/94 ALL Because of change in the number of grid points along latitude rows means for all fields start on 4/4/95 and are for 26 days at STEP=006 down to 17 at STEP=240.

6.2 Model level fields

6.2.1 Model level data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Times: 00, 06, 12, 18

- (a) Period: 7/85 (0000) - 4/86 (1800)
 Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 16
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

Exception conditions: None

- (b) Period: 5/86 (0000) - 3/87 (1800)
 Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 19
 Parameters: Same as for period 7/85 to 4/86

Exception conditions

5/86 ALL The new level definition was added on 13/5/86 so the analysis means for all fields are for 19 days.

- (c) Period: 4/87 (0000) - 8/91 (1800)
 Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 19
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

Exception conditions

4/87 ALL The new field 135 was added on 13/4/87 so all analysis means for that field are for 18 days.

- (d) Period: 9/91 (0000) - 7/94 (1800)
 Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 31
 Parameters: Same as for period 4/87 to 8/91

Exception conditions

9/91 ALL The new level definition was added on 17/9/91 so the analysis means for all fields are for 14 days.

- (e) Period: 8/94 (0000) - 3/95 (1800)
 Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 31
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Orography	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

Exception conditions

8/94 ALL The new level definition was added on 23/8/94 so the analysis means for all fields are for 9 days.

- (f) Period: 4/95 (0000) onward
 Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics

Levels: 1 to 31
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Orography	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

Exception conditions: None

Structure: Quasi-regular (reduced) N160 Gaussian Grid
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Specific humidity	133	Q

Exception conditions:
4/95 ALL The new field representation started on 4/4/95 so means are for 27 days.

6.2.2 Model level data - Initialised analysis

Times: 00, 06, 12, 18

- (a) Period: 7/85 (0000) - 4/86 (1800)
- Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
- Levels: 1 to 16
- Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

Exception conditions: None

- (b) Period: 5/86 (0000) - 3/87 (1800)
- Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
- Levels: 1 to 19
- Parameters: Same as for period 7/85 to 4/86

Exception conditions

5/86 ALL The new level definition was added on 13/5/86 so the analysis means for all fields are for 19 days.

- (c) Period: 4/87 (0000) - 8/91 (1800)

Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 19
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

Exception conditions

4/87 ALL The new field 135 was added on 13/4/87 so all analysis means for that field are for 18 days.

(d) Period: 9/91 (0000) - 3/95 (1800)
 Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 31
 Parameters: Same as for period 4/87 to 8/91

Exception conditions

9/91 ALL The new level definition was added on 17/9/91 so the analysis means for all fields are for 14 days.

(e) Period: 4/95 (0000) onward
 Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 31
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

Exception conditions: None

Structure: Quasi-regular (reduced) N160 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Specific humidity	133	Q
Cloud Liquid Water Content	246	CLWC
Cloud Ice Water Content	247	CIWC
Cloud Cover	248	CC

Exception conditions:

4/95 ALL The new field representation started on 4/4/95 so means are for 27 days.

6.2.3 Model level data - First Guess

Times: 00, 06, 12, 18

- (a) Period: 9/94(0000) - 3/95 (1800)
- Step: 06
- Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
- Levels: 1 to 31
- Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

Exception conditions: None

- (b) Period: 4/95(0000) - onward
- Step: 06
- Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
- Levels: 1 to 31
- Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

Exception conditions: None

Structure: Quasi-regular (reduced) N160 Gaussian Grid

Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Specific humidity	133	Q
Cloud Liquid Water Content	246	CLWC
Cloud Ice Water Content	247	CIWC
Cloud Cover	248	CC

Exception conditions:

4/95 ALL The new field representation started on 4/4/95 so means are for 27 days.

6.2.4 Model level data - Forecast

Time: 12

- (a) Period: 8/85 - 4/86
 Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 16
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

Exception conditions: None

- (b) Period: 5/86 - 3/87
 Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 19
 Parameters: Same as for period 7/85 to 4/86

Exception conditions

5/86 ALL The new level definition was added on 13/5/86 so the forecast means for all fields are for 19 days at STEP=006 down to 9 days at STEP=240.

- (c) Period: 4/87 - 8/91
 Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 19
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

Exception conditions

4/87 ALL The new field 135 was added on 13/4/87 so the forecast means for that field are for 18 days at STEP=006 down to 8 days at STEP=240.

- (d) Period: 9/91 - 3/95
 Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics

Levels: 1 to 31
 Parameters: Same as for period 4/87 to 8/91

Exception conditions

9/91 ALL The new level definition was added on 17/9/91 so the forecast means for all fields are for 14 days at STEP=006 down to 4 days at STEP=240.

(e) Period: 4/95 - onward
 Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 31
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

Exception conditions: None

Structure: Quasi-regular (reduced) N160 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Specific humidity	133	Q
Cloud Liquid Water Content	246	CLWC
Cloud Ice Water Content	247	CIWC
Cloud Cover	248	CC

Exception conditions:

4/95 ALL The new field representation started on 4/4/95 so means are for 27 days at STEP=006 down to 17 at STEP=240.

6.3 Pressure Level Fields

6.3.1 Pressure level data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Times: 00, 06, 12, 18

(a) Period: 7/85 (0000) - 9/91 (1800)
 Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 14-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T

Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D
Relative Humidity	157	R

Exception conditions

9/91 The model resolution changed to T213 spherical harmonics on 17/9/91, but the monthly means are calculated using T106 spherical harmonics for conformity with the data from the start of the month.

(b) Period: 10/91 (0000) - 11/91 (1800)
 Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 14-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
 Parameters: Same as for period 7/85 to 9/91

(c) Period: 12/91 (0000) - 3/95 (1800)
 Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 15-1000, 925, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
 Parameters: Same as for period 7/85 to 9/91

Exception conditions

12/91 ALL The new level (925) was added on 10/12/91 so analysis means for all fields are for 22 days.

(d) Period: 4/95 (0000) onward
 Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 15-1000, 925, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D
Relative Humidity	157	R

Exception conditions: None

Structure: Quasi-regular (reduced) N160 Gaussian Grid
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Specific humidity	133	Q

Exception conditions

4/95 ALL This field was added on 4/4/95 so analysis means are for 27 days.

6.3.2 Pressure level data - Initialised analysis

Times: 00, 06, 12, 18

- (a) Period: 7/85 (0000) - 9/91 (1800)
- Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
- Levels: 14-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
- Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D
Relative Humidity	157	R

Exception conditions

9/91 The model resolution changed to T213 spherical harmonics on 17/9/91, but the monthly means are calculated using T106 spherical harmonics for conformity with the data from the start of the month.

- (b) Period: 10/91 (0000) - 11/91 (1800)
- Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
- Levels: 14-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
- Parameters: Same as for period 7/85 to 9/91

Exception conditions: None

- (c) Period: 12/91 (0000) - 3/95 (1800)
- Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
- Levels: 15-1000, 925, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
- Parameters: Same as for period 7/85 to 9/91

Exception conditions

12/91 ALL The new level (925) was added on 10/12/91 so analysis means for all fields are for 22 days.

- (d) Period: 4/95 (0000) onward
- Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
- Levels: 15-1000, 925, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
- Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO

Divergence	155	D
Relative Humidity	157	R

Exception conditions: None

Structure: Quasi-regular (reduced) N160 Gaussian Grid

Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Specific humidity	133	Q

Exception conditions

4/95 ALL This field was added on 4/4/95 so initialised analysis means are for 27 days.

6.3.3 Pressure level data - First Guess

Times: 00, 06, 12, 18

- (a) Period: 9/94 - 3/95
 Step: 6
 Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 15-1000, 925, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D
Relative Humidity	157	R

Exception conditions: None

- (b) Period: 4/95 - onwards
 Step: 6
 Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 15-1000, 925, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

Relative Humidity 157 R

Exception conditions: None

Structure: Quasi-regular (reduced) N160 Gaussian Grid

Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Specific humidity	133	Q

Exception conditions

4/95 ALL This field was added on 4/4/95 so First Guess means are for 27 days.

6.3.4 Pressure level data - Forecast

Time: 12

- (a) Period: 8/85 - 9/91
- Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
- Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
- Levels: 14-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
- Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D
Relative Humidity	157	R

Exception conditions

4/88 Field 157 at STEP=216 and LEVELIST=10 has one missing data item. This is indicated in the GRIB header.

6/90 Field 135 at STEP=192 and LEVELIST=1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200 and 150 has one missing data item. This is indicated in the GRIB headers.

9/91 The model resolution changed to T213 spherical harmonics on 17/9/91, but the monthly means are calculated using T106 spherical harmonics for conformity with the data from the start of the month.

- (b) Period: 10/91 - 11/91
- Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
- Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
- Levels: 14-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10

Parameters: Same as for period 7/85 to 9/91

- (c) Period: 12/91 - 3/95
Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
Levels: 15-1000, 925, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
Parameters: Same as for period 7/85 to 9/91

Exception conditions

12/91 ALL The new level (925) was added on 10/12/91 so forecast means for all fields are for 22 days at STEP=006 down to 12 days at STEP=240.

- (d) Period: 4/95 onward
Step: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
Structure: T213 Spherical Harmonics
Levels: 15-1000, 925, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D
Relative Humidity	157	R

Exception conditions: None

Structure: Quasi-regular (reduced) N160 Gaussian Grid

Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Specific humidity	133	Q

Exception conditions

4/95 ALL This field was added on 4/4/95 so forecast means are for 27 days at STEP=06 down to 17 days at STEP=240..

7 CODES AND DATA UNITS

7.1 Fields

7.1.1 ECMWF local Code Table 2, Version Number 128 for FM 92-VIII Ext. GRIB

CODE FIGURE	MARS ABBREV.	FIELD	UNITS
127	AT	Atmospheric tide ⁺	-
128	BV	Budget values ⁺	-
129	Z	Geopotential (at the surface=orography)	m ² s ⁻²
130	T	Temperature	K
131	U	U-velocity	ms ⁻¹
132	V	V-velocity	ms ⁻¹
133	Q	Specific humidity	kg/kg
134	SP	Surface pressure	Pa
135	W	Vertical velocity	Pa s ⁻¹
136	TCW	Total column water	Kg/m ²
137	TCWV	Total column water vapour	Kg/m ²
138	VO	Vorticity (relative)	s ⁻¹
139	STL1	Soil temperature level 1	K
140	SWL1	Soil wetness level 1	m (of water)
141	SD	Snow depth	m (of water equivalent)
142	LSP	Large scale precipitation*	* m
143	CP	Convective precipitation*	* m
144	SF	Snow fall*	* m (of water equivalent)
145	BLD	Boundary layer dissipation*	* Wm ⁻² s
146	SSHF	Surface sensible heat flux*	* Wm ⁻² s
147	SLHF	Surface latent heat flux*	* Wm ⁻² s

151	MSL	Mean sea level pressure	Pa
152	LNSP	Log surface pressure	-
155	D	Divergence	s^{-1}
156	GH	Height (geopotential)	m
157	R	Relative humidity	%
158	TSP	Tendency of surface pressure	$Pa s^{-1}$
160	SDOR	Standard deviation of orography	-
161	ISOR	Anisotropy of subgrid scale orography	-
162	ANOR	Angle of subgrid scale orography	-
163	SLOR	Slope of subgrid scale orography	-
164	TCC	Total cloud cover	(0-1)
165	10U	10 metre u wind component	$m s^{-1}$
166	10V	10 metre v wind component	$m s^{-1}$
167	2T	2 metre temperature	K
168	2D	2 metre dewpoint temperature	K
170	STL2	Soil temperature level 2	K
171	SWL2	Soil wetness level 2 ⁺⁺	m (of water)
172	LSM	Land/sea mask	(0, 1)
173	SR	Surface roughness	m
174	AL	Albedo	-
176	SSR	Surface solar radiation*	$* Wm^{-2}s$
177	STR	Surface thermal radiation*	$* Wm^{-2}s$
178	TSR	Top solar radiation*	$* Wm^{-2}s$
179	TTR	Top thermal radiation*	$* Wm^{-2}s$
180	EWSS	East/West surface stress*	$* Nm^{-2}s$
181	NSSS	North/South surface stress*	$* Nm^{-2}s$
182	E	Evaporation*	*m(of water)
183	STL3	Soil temperature level 3	K

184	SWL3	Soil wetness level 3 ⁺⁺	m (of water)
185	CCC	Convective cloud cover	(0 - 1)
186	LCC	Low cloud cover	(0 - 1)
187	MCC	Medium cloud cover	(0 - 1)
188	HCC	High cloud cover	(0 - 1)
190	EWOV	EW component of sub-grid scale orographic variance	m ²
191	NSOV	NS component of sub-grid scale orographic variance	m ²
192	NWOV	NWSE component of sub-grid scale orographic variance	m ²
193	NEOV	NESW component of sub-grid scale orographic variance	m ²
195	LGWS	Latitudinal component of gravity wave stress*	* Nm ⁻² s
196	MGWS	Meridional component of gravity wave stress*	* Nm ⁻² s
197	GWD	Gravity wave dissipation*	* Wm ⁻² s
198	SRC	Skin reservoir content	m (of water)
199	VEG	Percentage of vegetation	%
200	VSO	Variance of sub-grid scale orography	m ²
201	MX2T	Maximum temp. at 2m since previous post-processing	K
202	MN2T	Minimum temp. at 2m since previous post-processing	K
204	PAW	Precip. analysis weights	-
205	RO	Runoff*	*m
228	TP	Total precipitation?	m
229	IEWS	Instantaneous X surface stress	N/m ²
230	INSS	Instantaneous Y surface stress	N/m ²
231	ISHF	Instantaneous surface heat flux	W/m ²
232	IE	Instantaneous moisture flux (evaporation)	Kg/m ² s
233	ASQ	Apparent surface humidity	Kg/Kg
234	LSRH	Logarithm of surface roughness length for heat.	-
235	SKT	Skin temperature	K

236	STL4	Soil temperature level 4	K
237	SWL4	Soil wetness level 4	m
238	TSN	Temperature of snow layer	K
239	CSF	Convective snow-fall*	m (of water equivalent)
240	LSF	Large scale snow-fall*	m (of water equivalent)
243	FAL	Forecast albedo	-
244	FSR	Forecast surface roughness	m
245	FLSR	Forecast logarithm of surface roughness for heat.	-
246	CLWC	Cloud liquid water content	Kg/Kg
247	CIWC	Cloud ice water content	Kg/Kg
248	CC	Cloud cover	0-1
250		Ice age (0 first-year, 1 multi-year)	1,0

- * Denotes field accumulated since start of forecast.
- + Denotes not GRIB data.
- ++ Scaled to the depth of the surface layer. The values can be interpreted as the amount of water in a layer 7cm deep.
- ? denotes not an archived field.

7.1.2 ECMWF local Code Table 2, Version Number 131 for FM 92-VIII Ext. GRIB

CODE-FIGURE	MARS ABBREV.	FIELD	UNITS	
				Threshold
130	TAP	Temperature anomaly probability	%	K
165	10SP	10 metre speed probability	%	m s ⁻¹
228	TTP	Total precipitation probability	%	m

7.2 Observations

Data types as defined in the BUFR form (Table A):

MARS abbreviation

LSD
SSD
VSNS
VSS
SLNS
SLS
OD
DD
SDS

Observation type

Land surface data
Sea surface data
Vertical soundings (not satellite)
Vertical soundings (satellite)
Single level upper-air (not satellite)
Single level upper-air (satellite)
Oceanographic data.
Derived data
Surface Data (Satellite)

Land surface data subtypes:

<u>Subtype number</u>	<u>MARS abbreviation</u>	<u>Subtype</u>
1	S	Synop land
2	S2	Synop record 2 land
3	SA	Synop auto land
4	SA2	Synop auto record 2 land

Sea surface data subtypes:

<u>Subtype number</u>	<u>MARS abbreviation</u>	<u>Subtype</u>
9	SAB	Synop ship abbreviated
11	SS	Synop ship
12	SS2	Synop record 2 ship
13	SAS	Synop auto ship
14	SAS2	Synop auto record 2 ship
19	SH	Shred
20	RCD	Reduced COADS data (SHIPS & BUOY)
21	DSU	Dribu surface
22	BSU	Bathy surface
23	TSU	Tesac surface

Vertical soundings (not satellite) subtypes:

<u>Subtype number</u>	<u>MARS abbreviation</u>	<u>Subtype</u>
91	P	Pilot land
92	PS	Pilot ship
95	WP	Wind profiler
101	T	Temp land
102	TS	Temp ship
103	TD	Temp drop
104	R	Rocob land
105	RS	Rocob ship

106 TM Temp mobile

Vertical soundings (satellite) subtypes:

<u>Subtype number</u>	<u>MARS abbreviation</u>	<u>Subtype</u>
51	HR	High resolution (120 km) (Soundings and brightness temperatures)
61	SMT	Sattem mean temp. (500 km low level)
62	SW	Sattem water (500 km low level)
63	SHL	Sattem higher level mean layer temperature (500 km)
71	MT	Mean temp. (250 km TOVS)
72	W	Water (250 km TOVS)
73	HL	Higher level (250 km TOVS)

Surface Data (Satellite)

<u>Subtype number</u>	<u>MARS abbreviation</u>	<u>Subtype</u>
121	WAS	Wave Scatterometer
122	WIS	Wind Scatterometer
123	RAL	Radar Altimeter
124	SST	Sea Surface Temperature
125	RW	Reprocessed Wind

Single level upper-air (not satellite) subtypes:

<u>Subtype number</u>	<u>MARS abbreviation</u>	<u>Subtype</u>
141	COD	Codar
142	AIR	Airep
143	COL	Colba
144	AM	AMDAR
145	AC	ACARS

Single level upper-air (satellite) subtypes:

<u>Subtype number</u>	<u>MARS abbreviation</u>	<u>Subtype</u>
82	SAT2	Satob section 2
83	SAT3	Satob section 3
84	SAT4	Satob section 4
85	SAT5	Satob section 5

Oceanographic subtypes:

<u>Subtype number</u>	<u>MARS abbreviation</u>	<u>Subtype</u>
-----------------------	--------------------------	----------------

131	DO	Dribu oceanographic
132	BO	Bathy "
133	TO	Tesac "

Derived data:

<u>Subtype number</u>	<u>MARS abbreviation</u>	<u>Subtype</u>
164	PA	PAOBS

8 OTHER ARCHIVES

8.1 5-Day Forecast Hourly Post-processing

The forecast from 1200 on 16/1/88 was run for 5 days with forecast timesteps archived at 1-hour intervals, i.e. STEP=1/TO/120/BY/1. These data have been archived as version 11, i.e. EXPVER=11 is required to retrieve the data.

8.2 TOGA Archive Contents

The TOGA (Tropical Oceans and Global Atmosphere) archive contains the data described below, which have been archived since 1/1/85. Retrieval is the same as for operational data, but with the following archive identification parameter settings:

STREAM=TOGA,REPRES=LL

8.2.1 Surface data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Times: 00, 12
Structure: 2.5 x 2.5 degree latitude/longitude grid, global fields
Parameter:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Land sea mask	172	LSM
Surface pressure	134	SP
Surface temperature	139	ST
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Geopotential (surface)	129	Z

8.2.2 Pressure level data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Times: 00, 12
Structure: 2.5 x 2.5 degree latitude/longitude grid, global fields
Levels: 14-1000, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 10 hPa
Parameter:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
u-velocity	131	U
v-velocity	132	V
Vertical velocity	135	W
Relative humidity	157	R

8.3 Chernobyl Archive Contents

A special data set covering the period 24/4/86 to 10/5/86 has been created and archived in MARS. To retrieve the data, **STREAM=CHERNOBYL** (or abbreviation **CH**) should be used in retrieval requests.

8.3.1 Model level data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Times: 00, 06, 12, 18
 Period: 24/4/86 to 10/5/86 inclusive
 Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 1 to 16
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Data</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Ln surface pressure	152	LNSP
Temperature	130	T
Specific humidity	133	Q
Vertical velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	VO
Divergence	155	D

8.3.2 Model level data - Forecast

Time: 12
 Steps: 6-hourly to HH+120, then 12-hourly to HH+240
 Period: 25/4/86 only
 Structure:)
 Levels:) As for the analysis
 Parameters:)

8.4 Monthly Climatology Data

STREAM=MO
 TYPE = CL
 Structure: T106 Spherical Harmonics
 Levels: 8-1000, 850, 700, 500, 300, 200, 100, 50 hPa
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T

8.5 Data from Other Centres

A selection of products, both analysis and forecast, from other centres are archived in MARS. These are a subset of products received, but all the most recent products are on the Fields Data Base (FDB) and may be accessed via MARS. Other centres' products may be retrieved by setting the parameter **STREAM=centre name** or **ICAO location identifier** and **REPRES=latitude longitude** or **ll**,

e.g. **STREAM=BRACKNELL,REPRES=ll**

or **STREAM=EGRR,REPRES=latitude longitude**

If any product is missing, a dummy field is archived, so users should check the number of values decoded, which is negative if the field is missing. These products are received in a number of parts and merged before insertion in the FDB, so it is possible that incomplete global fields are archived. Users should check the bit map to identify any points where data is missing.

Interpolation and conversion is not currently supported for GRIB data with bit maps.

8.5.1 Bracknell data

Location identifier is EGRR
Centre number is 74

8.5.1.1 Surface data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Times: 00, 12
Period: Last three years
Structure: 2.5/5.0 latitude/longitude grid

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL

8.5.1.2 Surface data - Forecast

Times: 00, 12
Period: Last three years
Steps: HH + 06, 12, 18, 24, 30, 36, 42, 48, 54, 60, 72, 96, 120, 144
Structure: 2.5/5.0 latitude/longitude grid.

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL

8.5.1.3 Pressure level data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Times: 00, 12
Period: Last three years
Structure: 2.5/5.0 latitude/longitude grid
Levels: 850, 700 and 500 hPa, but see below

<u>Level</u>	<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
850	Temperature	130	T
700	Relative humidity	157	R
500	Geopotential	129	Z

Also available from FDB only (most recent data) is geopotential at 1000, 700, 300, 100 and 50 hPa.

8.5.1.4 Pressure level data - Forecast

Times: 00, 12
Period: Last three years
Steps: HH + 06, 12, 18, 24, 30, 36, 42, 48, 54, 60, 72, 96, 120, 144
Structure: 2.5/5.0 latitude/longitude grid

Levels: 850, 700 and 500 hPa, but see below

<u>Level</u>	<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
850	Temperature	130	T
700	Relative humidity	157	R
500	Geopotential	129	Z

8.5.2 Washington data

Location identifier is KWBC
Centre number is 07

8.5.2.1 Surface data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Times: 00, 12
Period: Last three years
Structure: 5.0/5.0 latitude/longitude grid.

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL

8.5.2.2 Surface data - Forecast

Times: 00, 12
Period: Last three years
Steps: HH + 24, 48, 72
Structure: 5.0/5.0 latitude/longitude grid

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL

8.5.2.3 Pressure level data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Times: 00, 12
Period: Last three years
Structure: 5.0/5.0 latitude/longitude grid
Levels: 1000, 850 and 500 hPa, but see below.

<u>Level</u>	<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
1000	Geopotential	129	Z
850	Temperature	130	T
500	Geopotential	129	Z

Also available from FDB only (most recent data) are Z at 850, 700, 300, 200, 100 and 50 hPa, and T at 1000, 700, 500, 300, 200, 100 and 50 hPa.

8.5.2.4 Pressure level data - Forecast

Times: 00, 12
Period: Last three years
Steps: HH + 12, 24, 36, 48, 54, 60, 72, 96, 120, 144

(Temperature at 12, 24, 36 only)
 Structure: 5.0/5.0 latitude/longitude grid
 Levels: 1000, 850 and 500 hPa, but see below.

<u>Level</u>	<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
1000	Geopotential	129	Z
850	Temperature	130	T
500	Geopotential	129	Z

Also available from FDB only (most recent data) are Z at 850, 700, 300, 200, 100 and 50 hPa for steps HH + 12, 24, 36 and 48; T at 1000, 700, 500, 300, 200 and 100 hPa for steps HH + 12, 24 and 36; T at 250 hPa for steps HH + 24 and 36.

8.5.3 Offenbach data

Location identifier is EDZW
 Centre number is 78

8.5.3.1 Surface data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Times: 00, 12
 Period: Last three years
 Structure: 2.5/2.5 latitude/longitude grid.

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL

8.5.3.2 Surface data - Forecast

Times: 00, 12
 Period: Last three years
 Steps: HH + 12, 18, 24, 36, 48, 72, 96, 120, 144
 Time step 168 added on 1/2/93
 Structure: 2.5/2.5 latitude/longitude grid

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL

8.5.3.3 Pressure level data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Times: 00, 12
 Period: Last three years
 Structure: 2.5/2.5 latitude/longitude grid
 Level: 500 hPa

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z

Also available from FDB only (most recent data) is Z at 850, 700 and 300 hPa.

8.5.3.4 Pressure level data - Forecast

Times: 00, 12
 Period: Last three years
 Steps: HH + 12, 18, 24, 36, 48, 72, 96, 120, 144
 Time step 168 added on 1/2/93
 Structure: 2.5/2.5 latitude/longitude grid
 Level: 500 hPa

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z

Also available from FDB only (most recent data) is Z at 850, 700 and 300 hPa for steps HH + 12, 18, 24, 36, 48.

8.5.4 Paris data

Location identifier is LFPW
 Centre number is 84

8.5.4.1 Surface data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Time: 00
 Period: Last three years
 Structure: 2.5/2.5 latitude/longitude grid.

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL

8.5.4.2 Surface data - Forecast

Time: 00
 Period: Last three years
 Steps: HH + 24, 48, 72
 Structure: 2.5/2.5 latitude/longitude grid.

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL

8.5.4.3 Pressure level data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Time: 00
 Period: Last three years
 Structure: 2.5/2.5 latitude/longitude grid
 Level: 500 hPa

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z

8.5.4.4 Pressure level data - Forecast

Time: 00
 Period: Last three years
 Steps: HH + 24, 48, 72

Structure: 2.5/2.5 latitude/longitude grid
Level: 500 hPa

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z

8.5.5 Tokyo data

Location identifier is RJTD
Centre number is 34

8.5.5.1 Surface data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Time: 12
Period: Last three years
Structure: 5.0/5.0 latitude/longitude grid.

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL

8.5.5.2 Surface data - Forecast

Time: 12
Period: Last three years
Steps: HH + 24, 48, 72
Structure: 5.0/5.0 latitude/longitude grid.

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL

8.5.5.3 Pressure level data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Time: 12
Period: Last three years
Structure: 5.0/5.0 latitude/longitude grid
Level: 500 hPa

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z

8.5.5.4 Pressure level data - Forecast

Time: 12
Period: Last three years
Steps: HH + 24, 48, 72
Structure: 5.0/5.0 latitude, longitude grid
Level: 500 hPa

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
------------------	-------------------	---------------------

Geopotential 129 Z

8.5.6 Montreal data

Location identifier is CWAO
Centre number is 53

8.5.6.1 Surface data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Time: 00
Period: Last three years
Structure: 5.0/5.0 latitude/longitude grid

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL

8.5.6.2 Surface data - Forecast

Time: 00
Period: Last three years
Steps: HH + 24, 48, 72, 96, 120, 144
Structure: 5.0/5.0 latitude/longitude grid

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL

8.5.6.3 Pressure level data - Analysis (uninitialised)

Time: 00
Period: Last three years
Structure: 5.0/5.0 latitude/longitude grid
Level: 500 hPa

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z

8.5.6.4 Pressure level data - Forecast

Time: 00
Period: Last three years
Steps: HH + 24, 48, 72, 96, 120, 144
Structure: 5.0/5.0 latitude/longitude grid
Level: 500 hPa

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z

8.6 Ensemble Forecasts

An experimental Ensemble Prediction System (EPS) has been run on three consecutive days each week, producing products based on data for 1200 UTC on Saturday, Sunday and Monday, since 19 December 1992. Finally daily runs started on 1st of May 1994. These products are all archived, as are those from the pre-operational runs on 10,11,12 and 13 December 1992.

All forecasts are run at T63 resolution on 19 model levels. The EPS gives rise to many GRIB products which contain the same element at the same level and time, but from different forecasts. Local ECMWF extensions to Section 1 of the GRIB code have been made to correctly identify each product. See Appendix F for details.

To retrieve data, STREAM=ENSEMBLE FORECAST (or abbreviation EF) should be used.

8.6.1 Control Forecast

A full set of fields, identical to those for the Operational Forecast but at T63 (model and pressure levels) and N48 Gaussian Grid (surface and diagnostic parameter).

Use TYPE=CONTROL FORECAST (CF) in retrieval requests

8.6.2 Ensemble Perturbed forecasts

To retrieve data use

```

TYPE          = PERTURBED FORECAST(PF)
ENSEMBLE     = /* ensemble number(s)
              ALL
  
```

8.6.2.1 Pressure level data

```

Time:          12
Period:        01/05/94 onwards
Steps:         00 to HH+240 at 12 hourly intervals
Structure:     T63
Levels:        1000, 850, 700, 500, 200 hPa
Parameters:
  
```

	<u>Field code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	129	Z
Temperature	130	T
Specific Humidity	133	Q
Vertical Velocity	135	W
Vorticity	138	Vo
Divergence	155	D
Relative Humidity	157	R

8.6.2.2 Surface data

```

Time:          12
Period:        01/05/94 onwards
Steps:         00 to HH+240 at 12 hourly intervals
Structure:     N48 Gaussian Grid
Parameters:
  
```

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
--	-------------------	---------------------

Budget values	128	BV dummies on 15/6/94
Surface temperature	139	ST
Surface soil wetness	140	SSW
Snowdepth	141	SD
Large scale precipitation	142	LSP
Convective precipitation	143	CP
Snowfall	144	SF
Boundary layer dissipation	145	BLD
Surface sensible heat flux	146	SSHF
Surface latent heat flux	147	SLHF
Mean sea level pressure	151	MSL
Cloud cover (total)	164	TCC
Ten metre u	165	10U
Ten metre v	166	10V
Two metre temperature	167	2T
Two metre dewpoint	168	2D
Surface solar radiation	176	SSR
Surface thermal radiation	177	STR
Top solar radiation	178	TSR
Top thermal radiation	179	TTR
Gravity wave dissipation	197	GWD

Each forecast has an ensemble number contained in the GRIB header.

8.6.3 Cluster Products

Means and standard deviations for up to 6 clusters of ensemble forecasts.

To retrieve data use

REPRES	=	LAT/LONG	(LL)
TYPE	=	CLUSTER MEAN	(CM)
		CLUSTER STD DEVIATION	(CS)
CLUSTER	=	*/ * Cluster number(s)	
		ALL	

8.6.3.1 Pressure level data

- (a) Time: 12
 Period: 01/05/94 - 28/02/95
 Steps: HH+72, 84, 96, 108, 120, 132, 144, 156, 168
 Structure: 1.5/1.5 latitude/longitude grid
 Levels: 1000, 500 hPa for parameter 129
 850, 500 hPa for parameter 130
- Parameters:
- | | <u>Field Code</u> | <u>MARS Abbrev.</u> |
|--------------|-------------------|---------------------|
| Geopotential | 129 | Z |
| Temperature | 130 | T |
- Domain: General European Area [G] (75.0 30.0 -20.0 45.0) (default)
- (b) Period: 01/03/95 onwards

Steps: Same as previous period.
Structure: Same as previous period.
Levels: Same as previous period.
Parameters: Same as previous period.
Domain: North West Europe [A] (70.0 40.0 -27.5 10.0)
North East Europe [B] (72.5 50.0 0.0 45.0)
South West Europe [C] (57.5 32.5 -15.0 17.5)
South East Europe [D] (57.5 32.5 2.5 42.5)
General European Area [G] (75.0 30.0 -20.0 45.0) (default)

8.6.3.2 Surface data

Nil

8.6.4 Forecast Probabilities

Forecast probabilities exist for temperature at 850 hPa, precipitation and 10 metre wind speed (ECMWF Local Code Table 2, Version 131 for FM 92-VIII Ext. GRIB).

To retrieve data use

STREAM = ENSEMBLE FORECAST [EF]
TYPE = FORECAST PROBABILITY [FP]

PROBABILITY= *
//
ALL
(where * is the value for the forecast probability number)

Time: 12
Period: 22/01/94 onwards
Steps: 00 to HH+240 at 12 hourly intervals
Structure: 1.5/1.5 latitude/longitude grid
Levels: 850 hPa for parameter 130
Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Temperature	130	TAP
10 metre u wind component	165	10SP
Total precipitation	228	TPP

These fields can be retrieved in the usual way from Mars by using the specifications below.

Note 1

Forecast probability number for temperature at 850 hPa.

- 1 - cold anomaly of at least -8 degrees K
- 2 - cold anomaly of at least -4 degrees K
- 3 - warm anomaly of at least +4 degrees K

4 - warm anomaly of at least +8 degrees K

Forecast probability number for precipitation.

- 1 - precipitation of at least 1 mm in 24 hours
- 2 - precipitation of at least 5 mm in 24 hours
- 3 - precipitation of at least 10 mm in 24 hours
- 4 - precipitation of at least 20 mm in 24 hours

Forecast probability number for wind speed.

- 1 - wind speed at 10m of at least 10 m/s
- 2 - wind speed at 10m of at least 20 m/s

Note 2.

The required precision for the threshold value is achieved by scaling the units, in which the meteorological parameter itself is reported, by an appropriate power of 10 (which may be positive, negative or 0).

For example

Parameter number 228, total precipitation, is reported in units of metres. With $D = 3$ and Lower threshold = 2, the value of the lower threshold is $2 * (1 \text{ metre} / 10^{**3})$ or 2 mm.

Note 3.

Data values are percentage probabilities of the indicated meteorological parameter being above the Lower threshold or being below the Upper threshold or lying between the Upper and Lower thresholds.

8.6.5 Forecast Mean Probabilities

To retrieve data use

STREAM = ENSEMBLE FORECAST [EF]
 TYPE = FORECAST PROBABILITY [FP]

PROBABILITY= *

//**

ALL

(where * is the value for the forecast probability number)

Time: 12
 Period: 01/03/95 onwards
 Steps: 0607 (2 day product, days 6-7)
 0810 (3 day product, days 8-10)
 0610 (5 day product, days 6-10)

Structure: 1.5/1.5 latitude/longitude grid
 Levels: 850 hPa for parameter 130
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Temperature	130	TAP
Total precipitation	228	TPP

These fields can be retrieved in the usual way from Mars by using the specifications below:

Note 1

Forecast probability number for temperature at 850 hPa.

- 1 - average temperature at 12 UTC more than 2 degrees K below climate
- 2 - average temperature at 12 UTC more than 2 degrees K above climate

Forecast probability number for precipitation.

- 1 - no rain (defined as less than .1mm over period)
- 2 - mean precipitation rate less than 1mm/day
- 3 - mean precipitation rate greater than 3mm/day
- 4 - mean precipitation rate greater than 5mm/day

Note 2.

The required precision for the threshold value is archived by scaling the units, in which the meteorological parameter itself is reported, by an appropriate power of 10 (which may be positive, negative or 0).

For example

Parameter number 228, total precipitation, is reported in units of metres. With D = 4 and Lower threshold=1, the value of the lower threshold is $1 * (1 \text{ metre} / 10^{**4})$ or .1mm.

Note 3.

Data values are percentage probabilities of the indicated meteorological parameter being above the Lower threshold or being below the Upper threshold or lying between the Upper and Lower thresholds.

8.6.6 Ensemble Mean Forecasts

To retrieve data use

STREAM	= ENSEMBLE FORECAST	[EF]
TYPE	= FORECAST MEAN	[EM]
	FORECAST STD DEVIATION	[ES]

Time: 12
 Period: 01/03/95 onwards
 Steps: HH+12 to HH+240 at 12 hourly intervals
 Structure: 1.5/1.5 latitude/longitude grid
 Levels: Z at 1000 and 500hPa - T at 850 and 500
 Parameters:

	<u>Field Code</u>	<u>MARS Abbrev.</u>
Geopotential	128	Z
Temperature	130	T

9 ERROR AND OTHER MESSAGES

At the end of each MARS job a message or error summary is printed. Messages are divided into a number of general classes, and within each class individual errors or messages are printed for each request.

9.1 No Errors In Request

PPH1XX No errors reported by MARS/IBM

PSH1XX Request number 1, no errors in data transmission
PSH1XX Request number 2, no errors in data transmission
MCUN MARS/Cray ended. No error reported.

9.2 MARS System Error - Class 1

PPH1XX message class 01 received. MARS error - notify MARS group

Individual error codes and messages are then printed, e.g.

PSH1XX request number 1,RC=5001, RSC=0002
invalid parameter length

9.3 Network Errors - Class 2

PPH1XX message class 02 received. Network error.

Individual error codes and messages are then printed, e.g.

PSH1XX request number 1,RC=0022,RSC=0016
MARSPUT network connection broken

For network errors MARS retries a number of times, so the following messages may also appear:

NAFTXX MARS re-trying to IBM
maximum number of re-tries reached

9.4 User Errors - Class 3

PPH1XX message class 03 received. User error.

Individual error codes and messages are then printed, e.g.

PSH1XX request number 1,RC=5001,RC=0001
file to be archived does not exist.

9.5 CFS/CFSI Errors-class 4

PPH1XX message class 04 received. CFS/CFSI error.

Individual error codes and messages are then printed, e.g.

PSH1XX request number 1,RC=5004,RSC=0001
CFS file or node missing

9.6 Warning Message - Class 5

PPH1XX message class 05 received. Warning message.

Individual error codes and messages are then printed, e.g.

PSH1XXX request number 1,RC=5004,RSC=0000
data already archived

9.7 Informative Messages - Class 6

PSH1XX message class 06 received. Informative message
PSH1XX request number 1,RC=9011,RSC=9002
request needs 11 tapes
request needs 2 MSS cartridges.

9.8 Errors In Requests - Class 90 And 91

PPH1XX message class 91 received. See errors in requests.

Individual error codes and messages are then printed, e.g.

PSH1XX request number 1,RC=1000,RSC=0005
CMMCRCD invalid date - NOT 6 FIGURES.

9.9 MARS Cray Error Messages

The Cray module of MARS reports any file handling errors and prints self-explanatory messages.

APPENDIX • A CRAY RETRIEVAL EXAMPLES

The job commands below show the general layout of a Cray job to retrieve MARS data.

```
mars<<*eor
*
* directives with an asterisk in column 1 are comments
*
retrieve,-----,target="file1"
*
* each retrieve directive must have a target file
*
retrieve,-----,target="file2"
*
* retrieve and target may be abbreviated
*
ret,-----,ta="file3"
*
* must terminate with an end directive
*
end
*eor
```

This shows directives being taken from the jobs input stream. To take directives from a file use
MARS filename

If only a check on the validity of requests is required, terminate the set of RETRIEVE directives with
CHECKOUT instead of END.

The following examples illustrate the use of RETRIEVE directives' parameters and value pairs. MARS prints the request as given by the user, the request as interpreted and including default values (value abbreviations as given in section 2.3 are used) and finally informative, warning or error messages. If the value OFF is given for any parameter, the parameter=value pair is not printed.

Example 1: Retrieve data from a spherical harmonic archive to a target file, with data still in spherical harmonic form.

```
RETRIEVE,TYPE=INITIALISED ANALYSIS, LEVTYPE=PRESSURE LEVELS, commands
LEVELIST=ALL,REPRES=SPHERICAL HARMONICS,PARAM=ALL, entered
DATE=870920,TIME=00/06/12/18,STEP=00,TARGET="LOCAL" by user
```

request number 1

```
RETRIEVE,
CLASS      = OD,
TYPE       = IA,
STREAM     = DA,
EXPVER     = 1,
LEVTYPE    = PL,
LEVELIST   = ALL,
REPRES     = SH,
```



```

PARAM      = ALL,
DATE       = 870920,      command
TIME       = 00/06/12/18  interpreted
STEP       = 00,         by MARS
TARGET     = "LOCAL",
CFSPATH    = ""
FORMAT     = P,
RESOL      = AV,
ACCURACY   = N,
AREA       = G,
LAUNCH     = "",
USE        = N,
COSTONLY   = N
    
```

END

user command

MARS Messages after retrieval complete:

```

PPH1XX      No errors reported by MARS/IBM
PSH1XX      Request number 1, no errors in data retrieval
PPD1UN      Number of retrieved fields = 392
    
```

(a) In this example the user request is typed in full, simply to document the request. Using abbreviations and defaults it could be reduced to:

```

RET,LEVE=ALL,PAR=ALL,DA=870920,
TI=00/06/12/18,TA="LOCAL"
END
    
```

(b) To retrieve analysis data, use

```
TYPE=ANALYSIS          (TY=AN)
```

To retrieve first guess data, use

```
TYPE=FIRST GUESS      (TY=FG)
```

```
TIME=03
STEP=03/09
```

This retrieves a 3-hour and 9-hour forecast, both of which have a verifying time of 0300.

(c) To retrieve forecast data, use

```
TYPE=FORECAST,        (TY=FC)
TIME=12,              (TI=12)
STEP=                 (STE=)
```

with **STEP** set to required forecast timestep(s)

```

e.g.
STEP=ALL              (all timesteps)
STEP=24               (H+24)
STEP=24/36/48        (H+24, H+36, H+48)
STEP=12/TO/240/BY12  (omit 6-hourly steps).
    
```


- (d) To retrieve model level data, use

LEVTYPE=MODEL LEVEL (LEVT=ML)

- (e) Levels may be specified, if all levels are not required.

LEVTYPE=PRESSURE LEVELS, (LEVT=PL,)
LEVELIST=1000/700/500, (LEVE=1000/700/500,)

or

LEVTYPE=MODEL LEVELS, (LEVT=ML,)
LEVELIST=1/2/3, (LEVE=1/2/3,)

- (f) Parameters may be specified, if all parameters are not required.

PARAM=GEOPOTENTIAL/TEMPERATURE (PAR=Z/T,)
PARAM=GEOPOTENTIAL (PAR=Z)

- (g) If a list or range of dates is required, they can be specified as follows:

DATE=870920/870921 (DA=870920/870921)
DATE=870920/TO/870930 (DA=870920/TO/870930)
DATE=870920/TO/870930/BY/2 (DA=870920/TO/870930/BY/2)

- (h) If only one time is required, one time may be specified, e.g.

TIME=12 (TI=12)
TIME=18 (TI=18)

- (i) Unpacked data may be obtained by using

FORMAT=UNPACKED (F=U)

- (j) The resolution of retrieved data can be reduced from that of the archived data by specifying the required resolution, e.g.

RESOL=63 (RES=63)

- (k) The number of bits used to store packed values may be reduced, e.g.

ACCURACY=REDUCED (AC=R)
ACCURACY=LOW (AC=L)
ACCURACY=12 (AC=12)

Example 2: Retrieve data from a spherical harmonic format archive and produce a target file with data in latitude/longitude grid format, for a sub-area.

RET,DATE=870820,TARGET="TEST4D",FORMAT=PACKED,
LEVTYPE=PL,LEVELIST=1000,REPRES=SH,TIME=12,TYPE=FC,PARAM=Z,

STEP=30,GRID=2.5/2.5,AREA=0/0/-11./11

request number 1

```

RETRIEVE,
  CLASS      =   OD,
  TYPE       =   FC,
  STREAM     =   DA,
  EXPVER     =   1,
  LEVTYPE    =   PL,
  LEVELIST   =   1000,
  REPRES     =   SH,
  PARAM      =   Z,
  DATE       =   870820,
  TIME       =   12,
  STEP       =   30,
  TARGET     =   "TEST4D",
  CFSPATH    =   "",
  FORMAT     =   P,
  RESOL      =   AV,
  ACCURACY   =   N,
  AREA       =   0/0/-11./11,
  GRID       =   2.5/2.5,
  LAUNCH     =   "",
  USE        =   N,
  COSTONLY   =   N
    
```

END

PPH1XX No errors reported by MARS/IBM

PSH1XX Request number 1, no errors in data transmission

PPD1UN Number of retrieved fields = 1

SETLIM Southern latitude changed to -12.500 from -11.000

SETLIM Eastern longitude changed to 12.500 from 11.000

(a) All the notes on parameters and values in example 1 are also applicable here.

(b) The AREA specification requests an area 0°N/0°W to 11°S/11°E. MARS has modified this area to provide consistency with the grid-mesh specified. Predefined areas may also be used, e.g.

AREA=GLOBAL (AR=G)

AREA=EUROPE (AR=E)

(c) The GRID parameter specifies the output field grid-mesh. As two values have been provided, a latitude/longitude grid field is provided.

To generate an output Gaussian grid field a single integer value should be used. To produce an N80 Gaussian grid use

GRID=80 (G=80)

Example 3: Retrieve data from surface, Gaussian grid archive


```
RET,DATE=870820,TARGET="TEST5A",FORMAT=PACKED,  
LEVTYPE=SFC,LEVELIST=OFF,REPRES=GG,TIME=12,TYPE=FC,PARAM=MSL/2T/2D,  
STEP=30,AREA=GLOBE,GRID=AV
```

request number 1

```
RETRIEVE,  
  CLASS      =  OD,  
  TYPE       =  FC,  
  STREAM     =  DA,  
  EXPVER     =  1,  
  LEVTYPE    =  SFC,  
  REPRES     =  GG,  
  PARAM      =  MSL/2T/2D,  
  DATE       =  870820,  
  TIME       =  12,  
  STEP       =  30,  
  TARGET     =  "TEST5A",  
  CFSPATH    =  "",  
  FORMAT     =  P,  
  ACCURACY   =  N,  
  AREA       =  G,  
  GRID       =  AV,  
  LAUNCH     =  "",  
  USE        =  N,  
  COSTONLY   =  N
```

END

- (a) This example retrieves data in exactly the same format as that of the archived data.
- (b) For Gaussian surface data set RESOL=OFF and LEVELIST=OFF.
- (c) Notes re parameters and values in examples 1 and 2 apply also to Gaussian data.

Example 4: Retrieve data to 1 target file, using several retrieve directives.

```
RET,TARG="TEMP",DATE=-2,CFSPATH="/HAR/COS/IA07"
```

request number 1

```
RETRIEVE,  
  CLASS      =  OD,  
  TYPE       =  IA,  
  STREAM     =  DA,  
  EXPVER     =  1,  
  LEVTYPE    =  PL,  
  LEVELIST   =  1000/850/700/500/400/300,  
  REPRES     =  SH,  
  PARAM      =  Z,  
  DATE       =  880307,  
  TIME       =  12,  
  STEP       =  00,  
  TARGET     =  "TEMP",  
  CFSPATH    =  "/HAR/COS/IA07"
```



```

FORMAT      = P,
RESOL       = AV,
ACCURACY    = N,
AREA        = G,
LAUNCH      = "",
USE         = N,
COSTONLY    = N
    
```

RET,TARG="TEMP",DATE=-3,CFSPATH="/HAR/COS/IA08"

request number 2

RETRIEVE,

```

CLASS       = OD,
TYPE        = IA,
STREAM      = DA,
EXPVER      = 1,
LEVTYPE     = PL,
LEVELIST    = 1000/850/700/500/400/300,
REPRES      = SH,
PARAM       = Z,
DATE        = 880306,
TIME        = 12,
STEP        = 00,
TARGET      = "TEMP",
CFSPATH     = "/HAR/COS/IA08"
FORMAT      = P,
RESOL       = AV,
ACCURACY    = N,
AREA        = G,
LAUNCH      = "",
USE         = N,
COSTONLY    = N
    
```

PPH1XX No errors reported by MARS/IBM

PSH1XX Request number 1, no errors in data transmission

PPD1UN Number of retrieved fields = 6

PSH1XX Request number 2, no errors in data transmission

PPD1UN Number of retrieved fields = 6.

APPENDIX•B EXAMPLE JOB USING PACKED DATA - FIELDS

```
:
#
# Job to retrieve packed fields from MARS, decode and print
# Sections 1 and 2 of GRIB data
#
# QSUB -A XXXXX      # Set account
#
# QSUB -s /bin/sh    # Change to Bourne Shell
#
# QSUB -e err01      # stderr file
#
# QSUB -o out01      # stdout file
#
# QSUB
#
# Target file to be deleted at end of job
#
cd $TMPDIR
#
# MARS request
#
mars << *eor
ret,target="myfile",
typ=an,date=901010,param=msl/10u/10v,level=off,
levtype=surface,repres=gg
end
*eor
#
# Check that MARS step completed correctly
#
if [ $? != 0 ]
    then
        echo "MARS request failed."
        exit
    fi
#
# User program
#
cat >grdemo.f <<EOF
PROGRAM GRDEMO
C
C**** GRDEMO - Program to demonstrate use of GRIBEX routine.
C
C Purpose.
C -----
C
```



```

C   Demonstrates use of GRIBEX routine to unpack
C   GRIB coded data.
C
C** Interface.
C   -----
C
C   File of GRIB coded data attached as unit 11.
C
C Method.
C   -----
C
C   Prints sections 0, 1, 2, 3 and 4 of GRIB message.
C
C Externals.
C   -----
C
C   GRIBEX
C   GRPRS0
C   GRPRS1
C   GRPRS2
C   GRPRS3
C   GRPRS4
C
C Reference.
C   -----
C
C   WMO Manual on Codes for GRIB definition.
C   WMO Publication No. 9, Volume B, for grid catalogue numbers.
C
C Comments.
C   -----
C
C   GRIBEX provides a number of packing/unpacking options.
C   See documentation in routine GRIBEX for details.
C
C Author.
C   -----
C
C   J. Hennessy   ECMWF   25.06.91
C
C Modifications.
C   -----
C
C   None.
C
C -----
C
C   Arrays are dimensioned to accommodate T213/N160 data volumes.
    
```



```
C
PARAMETER (JPACK=52000)
C
C   Array for integer parameters from section 0 of GRIB message.
C
C   DIMENSION ISEC0(2)
C
C   Array for integer parameters from section 1 of GRIB message.
C
C   DIMENSION ISEC1(32)
C
C   Array for integer parameters from section 2 of GRIB message.
C
C   DIMENSION ISEC2(384)
C
C   Array for integer parameters from section 3 of GRIB message.
C
C   DIMENSION ISEC3(2)
C
C   Array for integer parameters from section 4 of GRIB message.
C
C   DIMENSION ISEC4(42)
C
C   Array for real parameters from section 2 of GRIB message.
C
C   DIMENSION ZSEC2(96)
C
C   Array for real parameters from section 3 of GRIB message.
C
C   DIMENSION ZSEC3(2)
C
C   Array for real parameters from section 4 of GRIB message.
C   This is the binary data section and the array to hold
C   the unpacked data may need to be 4 times as long as that
C   for the packed data.
C
C   DIMENSION ZSEC4(JPACK*4)
C
C   Array to read in packed data.
C
C   DIMENSION INBUFF(JPACK)
C
C   GRIBEX routine has a number of different options.
C
C   CHARACTER*1 YOPER
C
C   Clear error counter.
C
C   NUMERR = 0
```



```
C
C      Lengths of INBUFF and PSEC4
C
C      ILENB = JPACK
C      IPUNP = JPACK * 4
C
C      Read packed field into INBUFF. THIS READ IS FOR CRAY BLOCKED
C      FILES AND SHOULD BE SUBSTITUTED BY APPROPRIATE READ FOR
C      OTHER FILE TYPES OR MACHINES.
C
50     CONTINUE
      BUFFER IN (11,1) (INBUFF(1),INBUFF(ILENB))
C
C      IF (UNIT(11)) 100,200,300
100    CONTINUE
C
C      'D' function to unpack entire GRIB message.
C
C      YOPER = 'D'
C      WRITE (*,9000)
C      WRITE (*,9001) YOPER
C
C      IERR = 1
C      CALL GRIBEX (ISEC0,ISEC1,ISEC2,ZSEC2,ISEC3,ZSEC3,ISEC4,
C                  ZSEC4,IPUNP,INBUFF,ILENB,IWORD,YOPER,IERR)
C
C      Check return code.
C
C      WRITE (*,9004) IERR
C      IF (IERR.EQ.-6) WRITE (*,*) ' GRDEMO : Pseudo-grib data found.'
C      IF (IERR.GT.0)
C      THEN
C      NUMERR = NUMERR + 1
C      GO TO 50
C      ENDIF
C
C      Print section 0, 1, 2 and 3 (if present) and 4.
C      Section 1 is the product definition section.
C      Section 2 is the grid definition section.
C      Section 3 is the bit-map section.
C      Section 4 is the data section.
C
C      CALL GRPRS0 (ISEC0)
C      CALL GRPRS1 (ISEC0,ISEC1)
C
C      IF (ISEC1(5).EQ.0.OR.ISEC1(5).EQ.64)
C      THEN
C      WRITE (*,9000)
C      WRITE (*,*) ' GRDEMO : No section 2 in GRIB message.'
```



```
ELSE
CALL GRPRS2 (ISEC0,ISEC2,ZSEC2)
ENDIF
C
IF (ISEC1(5).EQ.0.OR.ISEC1(5).EQ.128)
C THEN
WRITE (*,9000)
WRITE (*,*) 'GRDEMO : No section 3 in GRIB message.'
ELSE
CALL GRPRS3 (ISEC0,ISEC3,ZSEC3)
ENDIF
C
CALL GRPRS4 (ISEC0,ISEC4,ZSEC4)
C
GO TO 50
C
200 CONTINUE
C
WRITE (*,9000)
WRITE (*,9000)
WRITE (*,9002) NUMERR
C
STOP
C
300 STOP 'Read error'
C
9000 FORMAT (1H)
9001 FORMAT (1H,'GRDEMO : Function code = ',A)
9002 FORMAT (1H,'GRDEMO : Number of decoding errors = ',I9)
9004 FORMAT (1H,'GRDEMO : GRIBEX return code = ',I4)
C
END

EOF
#
# Compile program.
#
cft77 -e sxz grdemo.f
#
# Connect target file as unit 11.
#
assign -a myfile fort.11
#
# Load program and required libraries.
# Library EMOSLIB contains unpacking and printing software.
segldr -l $EMOSLIB, $ECLIB grdemo.o
#
# Execute program.
./a.out
```


APPENDIX • C CRAY EXAMPLE JOB USING UNPACKED DATA - FIELDS

```
:
#
# Job to retrieve unpacked fields from MARS, extract and print
# Sections 1 and 2 of GRIB data
#
# QSUB -A XXXXX      # Set account
#
# QSUB -s /bin/sh    # Change to Bourne Shell
#
# QSUB -e err01      # stderr file
#
# QSUB -o out01      # stdout file
#
# QSUB
#
# Target file to be deleted at end of job
cd $TMPDIR
#
# MARS request
#
mars << *eor
ret,date=910107,target="myfile",format=unpacked,
levtype=ml,level=1/2/3,param=temperature
end
*eor
cat >test.f <<EOF
    PROGRAM TEST
C
C*****
C*
C*   Name       :   TEST
C*
C*   Function    :   Demonstrates use of unpacked data.
C*
C*   Input       :   Data file attached as unit 11
C*
C*   Output      :   Prints sections 1 and 2 of GRIB fields.
C*
C*****
C
C
C
    DIMENSION ARRAY(54000)
    DIMENSION IARRAY(54000)
    DIMENSION FPD(210000)
    DIMENSION IB1(18),IB2(12)
    DIMENSION FB2(40)
C
```



```
      EQUIVALENCE (ARRAY(1),IARRAY(1))
C
100  BUFFER IN (11,1) (ARRAY(1),ARRAY(54000))
C
      IF (UNIT(11)) 200,900,999
C
200  CONTINUE
C
      IPR = 0
C
C      Parameters from section 1.
C
      CALL GETIB1 (LIB1,IB1,18,ARRAY,IPR,IERR)
      WRITE (*,9001) IERR
9001  FORMAT (1H,'GETIB1 return code = ',I4)
C
C      Print section 1, product definition section.
C
      CALL PRFBK1 (IB1)
C
C      Parameters from section 2.
C
      CALL GETIB2 (LIB2,IB2,12,ARRAY,IPR,IERR)
      WRITE (*,9002) IERR
9002  FORMAT (1H,'GETIB2 return code = ',I4)
C
C      Print section 2, grid definition section.
C
      CALL PRFBK2 (IB2)
C
C      Vertical parameters from section 2.
C
      CALL GETFB2 (LFB2,FB2,40,ARRAY,IPR,IERR)
      WRITE (*,9003) IERR
9003  FORMAT (1H,'GETFB2 return code = ',I4)
C
C      Floating point data.
C
      CALL GETFPD (LFPD,FPD,54000,ARRAY,IPR,IERR)
      WRITE (*,9004) IERR
9004  FORMAT (1H,'GETFPD return code = ',I4)
C
      GO TO 100
C
900  STOP
C
999  STOP 'Read error'
      END
EOF
```



```
#  
# Compile program  
cft77 -e fsxz test.f  
#  
# Connect target file as unit 11.  
assign -a myfile fort.11  
#  
# Load program and required libraries.  
# Library EMOSLIB contains extraction and printing software.
```


APPENDIX•D CRAY RETRIEVAL EXAMPLES - OBSERVATIONS

```
:
#
# Job to retrieve observations from MARS
#
# QSUB -A XXXXXX# Set account
#
# QSUB -s /bin/sh # Change to Bourne Shell
#
# QSUB -eo
#
# QSUB -o listobs
#
# QSUB -lt 50
#
# QSUB
#
# Target file to be deleted at end of job
#
cd $TMPDIR
#
# MARS request
#
mars <<eor
*
* vertical sounding non-satellite data for Northern Hemisphere
* octant 1
*
ret,type=obs,repr=bufr,time=0901/ta/1200,
obstype=vsns,area=n1,
target="myfile",date=910703
end
eor
#
cat > rdbuf.f <<EOF
PROGRAM RDBUFR
C
C**** *RDBUFR*
C
C
C Purpose
C -----
C
C Purpose of this program is to demonstrate use of
C packed BUFR data
C
C** Interface
```



```

C -----
C
C File of packed BUFR data attached as unit 4
C
C
C
C
C
C
C PARAMETER(JSUP = 9,JSEC0= 3,JSEC1= 40,JSEC2= 64 ,JSEC3= 4,
1 JSEC4= 2,JELEM=8000,JSUBS=400,JCVAL=150 ,JBUFL= 8192,
2 JBPW = 64,JTAB = 1000,JCTAB=120,JCTST=1800,JCTEXT= 200,
3 JWORK=80000,JKEY=46)
C
C PARAMETER (KDLEN=2,KELEM=8000,KVALS=80000,KVALS1=80000)
C
C KELEM can be set to
C
C KELEM = 350 for the most of data types
C = 2700 for the temp data
C
C LOGICAL OENC,OPRT
C CHARACTER*51 CF
C DIMENSION KBUFF(JBUFL)
C DIMENSION KBUFR(JBUFL)
C
C CHARACTER*64 CNames(KELEM)
C CHARACTER*24 CUnits(KELEM)
C CHARACTER*80 CVals(KVALS)
C CHARACTER*80 CVal(KVALS1)
C CHARACTER*80 YENC
C
C DIMENSION KSup(JSUP) ,KSEC0(JSEC0),KSEC1(JSEC1)
C DIMENSION KSEC2(JSEC2),KSEC3(JSEC3),KSEC4(JSEC4)
C DIMENSION KEY (JKEY)
C
C DIMENSION Values(KVALS),VALUE(KVALS1),VALUES2(KVALS1)
C DIMENSION KTDLST(KELEM),KTDEXP(KELEM),KRQ(KELEM),RQV(KELEM)
C DIMENSION KDATA(KDLEN)
C
C DATA CNames/KELEM*' ',CUnits/KELEM*' '
C
C RVIND is missing value indicator
C
C RVIND=1.7E38
C KRQL=0
C
C 50 CONTINUE
C
C 100 CONTINUE
C

```



```
C      Use buffer in for blocked files
C
C      BUFFER IN (4,1) (KBUFF(1),KBUFF(8192))
C      KBUFL=LENGTH(71)
C      PRINT*,' Length of message is ',KBUFL,' bytes'
C
C      IF(KBUFL.EQ.0) GO TO 200
C
C      N=N+1
C
C      PRINT*,'Bulletin number----->',N
C
C      Expand only section 0,1 and 2
C
C      CALL BUS012(KBUFL,KBUFF,KSUP,KSEC0,KSEC1,KSEC2,IERR)
C      IF(IERR.NE.0.AND.N.GT.1) CALL ABORT
C      To expand complete bufr message
C      CALL BUFREX(KBUFL,KBUFF,KSUP,KSEC0 ,KSEC1,KSEC2 ,KSEC3 ,KSEC4,
1     KELEM,CNAMES,CUNITS,KVALS,VALUES,CVALS,IERR)
C
C      IF(IERR.NE.0) THEN
C      IERR=0
C      GO TO 100
C      END IF
C
C      Print section 0
C
C      CALL BUPRS0(KSEC0)
C
C      Print section 1
C
C      CALL BUPRS1(KSEC1)
C
C      Unpack RDB key
C
C      CALL BUUKEY(KSEC1,KSEC2,KEY,KSUP,KERR)
C
C      Print key
C
C      CALL BUPRS2(KSUP ,KEY)
C
C      Get lists of packed and expanded data descriptors
C
C      CALL BUSEL(KTDLEN,KTDLST,KTDEXL,KTDEXP,KERR)
C
C      Print section 3
C
C      CALL BUPRS3(KSEC3,KTDLEN,KTDLST,KTDEXL,KTDEXP,KELEM,CNAMES)
C
```



```
C      To print expanded data the following can be used. It is commented out because it generates
C      a lot of printout.
C
C      CALL BUPRT(0,KSUB1,KSUB2,KELEM,CNAMES,CUNITS,CVALS,
C 1      KVALS,VALUES,KSUP,KSEC1,IERR)
C      KSUB1 - Starting subset to print, KSUB2 - Ending subset to print.
C      GO TO 100
C
C 200  CONTINUE
C
C      IF(IERR.EQ.-1) THEN
C      PRINT*, 'Number of records processed ',N
C      ELSE
C      PRINT*, ' Error ',IERR
C      END IF
C      PRINT*, 'Number of records processed ',N
C
C      END

EOF
#
#
assign -a myfile fort.4
#
#Compile and run program
#
cft77 -e sxz rdbuf.f
segldr -l $EMOSLIB, $ECLIB rdbuf.o
./a.out
```


APPENDIX • E GRIB CODE EDITIONS DIFFERENCES

In the table below, covering sections 0 and 1 of the GRIB code, octet numbering is from the beginning of the GRIB message;

* indicates that the value is not available in the code edition;

R indicates reserved, should be set to 0.

Experimental edition is considered as edition -1.

GRIB code edition -1 has fixed length of 20 octets for section 1, the length not included in the message. GRIB code edition 0 has fixed length of 24 octets for section 1, the length being included in the message. GRIB code edition 1 can have different lengths for section 1, the minimum being 28 octets, length being included in the message.

Contents	Octet numbers for code editions		
	-1	0	1
Letters GRIB	1-4	1-4	1-4
Total length of GRIB message	*	*	5-7
GRIB code edition number	*	*	8
Length of Section 1	*	5-7	9-11
Reserved octet (R)	*	8(R)	*
Version no. of Code Table 2	*	*	12
Identification of centre	5	9	13
Generating process	6	10	14
Grid definition	7	11	15
Flag (Code Table 1)	8	12	16
Indicator of parameter	9	13	17
Indicator of type of level	10	14	18
Height, pressure etc. of levels	11-12	15-16	19-20
Year of century	13	17	21
Month	14	18	22
Day	15	19	23
Hour	16	20	24
Minute	17	21	25
Indicator of unit of time	18	22	26
P1 - Period of time	19	23	27
P2 - Period of time	20(R)	24	28
or reserved octet (R)			
Time range indicator	21(R)	25	29
or reserved octet (R)			
Number included in average	22-23(R)	26-27	30-31
or reserved octet (R)			
Number missing from average	24(R)	28(R)	32
or reserved octet (R)			
Century of data	*	*	33
Reserved. Set to 0	*	*	34
Decimal scale factor	*	*	35-36
Reserved. Set to 0	*	*	37-48
(Need not be present)			
For originating centre use only	*	*	49-nn
(Need not be present)			

TABLE 1: Flag indication relative to Sections 2 and 3

GRIB Experimental Edition:

Code	Section 3	Section 2
0	Omitted	Omitted
1	Omitted	Included
2	Included	Omitted
3	Included	Included

GRIB Edition 0 and Edition 1:

Bit	Value	Meaning
1	0	Section 2 omitted
	1	Section 2 included
2	0	Section 3 omitted
	1	Section 3 included
3-8	0	

NOTE: Bits enumerated from left to right

TABLE 2: Indicator of parameter

MARS has always used the ECMWF Local Tables. See 7.0

TABLE 3: Fixed levels or layers for which the data are included

GRIB Experimental Edition:

Code Figs	Octet No. 10 Meaning	Octet No. 11 Contents	Octet No. 12
0	special level (as code table 0491)	0	0
99			
100	isobaric level	pressure in kPa	(2 octets)
101	layer between two isobaric levels	pressure of top (hPa)	pressure of bottom (kPa)
102	mean sea level	0	0
103	fixed height level (above mean sea level)	height (m) above MSL	(2 octets)
104	layer between two fixed height levels	height of top (hm above MSL)	height of bottom (hm above MSL)
105	layer between two fixed height levels	height of top (hm above ground)	height of bottom (hm above ground)
107	sigma level	sigma value in 1/10000	(2 octets)
108	layer between two sigma levels	sigma at top (1/100)	sigma at bottom (1/100)
109	hybrid level	level number	(2 octets)
110	layer between two hybrid levels	level no. of top	level no. of bottom

GRIB Edition 0

Code Figs.	Octet number 10 Meaning	Octet number 11 Contents	Octet number 12
00	-		
01	Ground surface		
02	Cloud base level		

03	Level of cloud tops	0	0
04	Level of 0°C isotherm		
05	Level of adiabatic condensation		
06	Maximum wind level		
07	Tropopause		
08)			
.)			
99)	Reserved		
100	Isobaric level	pressure in hPa	(2 octets)
101	Layer between 2 isobaric levels	pressure of top kPa	pressure of bottom kPa
102	Mean sea level	0	0
103	Fixed height level (above MSL)	height above MSL in metres	(2 octets)
104	Layer between two fixed height levels (above MSL)	height of top (hm above MSL)	height of bottom (hm above MSL)
105	Fixed height level (above ground)	height in metres	(2 octets)
106	Layer between 2 fixed height levels (above ground)	height of top (hm above ground)	height of bottom (hm above ground)
107	Sigma level	sigma value in 1/10000	(2 octets)
108	Layers between 2 sigma levels	sigma value of top in 1/100	sigma value of bottom in 1/100
109	Hybrid level	level number	(2 octets)
110	Layer between two hybrid levels	level no. of top	level no. of bottom
111)			
.)	Reserved		
254)			

GRIB Edition 1

Code Figs	Octet Number 10 Meaning	Octet Number 11 Contents	Octet Number 12 Contents
00	-		
01	Ground surface		
02	Cloud base level		
03	Level of clouds tops	0	0
04	Level of 0° isotherm		
05	Level of adiabatic condensation		
06	Maximum wind level		
07	Tropopause		
08)			
.)	Reserved		
99)			
100	Isobaric surface	pressure in hPa	(2 octets)
101	Layer between 2 isobaric surfaces	pressure of top kPa	pressure of bottom kPa
102	Mean sea level	0	0
103	Specified altitude	altitude in metres	(2 octets)
104	Layer between 2 specified altitudes	altitude of top (in hm)	altitude of bottom (in hm)
105	Specified height level (above ground)	height in metres	(2 octets)
106	Layer between 2 specified height levels (above ground)	height of top (in hm)	height of bottom (in hm)
107	Sigma level	sigma value in 1/10000	(2 octets)
108	Layers between 2 sigma levels	sigma value of top in 1/100	sigma value of bottom in 1/100
109	Hybrid level	level number	(2 octets)

110	Layer between two hybrid levels	level no. of top	level no. of bottom
111	Depth below land surface	Depth (cm)	(2 octets)
112	Layer between 2 depths below land surface	depth of upper surface (cm)	depth of lower surface (cm)
113			
.)	Reserved		
120			
121	Layer between 2 isobaric surfaces (high precision)	1100 hPa minus pressure of top in hPa	1100 hPa minus pressure of bottom in hPa
122			
.)	Reserved		
127			
128	Layer between 2 sigma surfaces (high precision)	1.1 minus sigma of top in 1/1000 of sigma	1.1 minus sigma of bottom in 1/1000 of sigma
129			
.)	Reserved		
140			
141	Layer between 2 isobaric surfaces (mixed precision)	Pressure of top in kPa	1100 hPa minus pressure of bottom in hPa
142			
.)	Reserved		
159			
160	Depth below sea level	Depth in metres	(2 octets)
161			
.)	Reserved		
.254			

TABLE 4: Unit of time
GRIB Experimental Edition

Code	Meaning
0	Minute
1	Hour
2	Day
3	Month
4	Year
5	Decade (10 years)
6	Normal (30 years)
7	Century (100 years)
8	)
to	)Reserved
29	)
30	Minute
31	5 minutes
32	10 minute
33	15 minute
34	20 minute
35	30 minute
36	)
to	) Reserved
39	)
40	Hour
41	2 hour
42	3 hour
43	4 hour
44	6 hour

45	8 hour
46	12 hour
47	)
to	) Reserved
49	)
50	Day
51	2 day
52	3 day
53	4 day
54	5 day
55	6 day
56	7 day
57	10 day
58	30 day
59	Reserved
60	month
61	2 month
62	3 month
63	4 month
65	6 month
66	8 month
67	10 month
70	year
71	2 year
72	3 year
73	4 year
74	5 year
75	)

to	Reserved
79	)
80	Decade (10 years)
81	20 year
82	30 year
83	)
to	)Reserved
89	)
90	Century (100 years)

GRIB Edition 0 and Edition 1

Code	Meaning
0	Minute
1	Hour
2	Day
3	Month
4	Year
5	Decade (10 years)
6	Normal (30 years)
7	Century (100 years)
8)	)
.)	Reserved
253)	
254	Second

TABLE 5: Time range indicator**GRIB Experimental Edition**

Code	Meaning
0	Product valid for time T1
1	Average (time T1 to time T2)
2	Accumulation (time T1 to time T2)
3	Difference (time T2 - time T1)
	...
10	Time 1 occupies 2 octets (octets 19 and 20). Product valid for time T1

NOTES:

1. Time T1 is obtained by adding time 1 to the reference time.
2. Time T2 is obtained by adding time 2 to the reference time.
3. For analysis products time 1 will be zero.
4. For forecast products time 1 will indicate the forecast period; the reference time will be the valid time of the initial data on which the forecast was based.
5. Provision is made to extend time 1 over two octets to assist with extended range forecasts.

GRIB Edition 0

Code	Meaning
0	Product valid for time T1
1	Initialised analysis product valid time T1
2	Range time between time T1 and time T2
3	Average (time T1 to time T2)
4	Accumulation (time T1 to time T2)
5	Difference (time T2 - time T1)
6	
.	Reserved
9	

10	Time 1 occupies 2 octets (octets 19 and 20). Product valid for time T1
11	
.	
254	

NOTES:

1. Time T1 is obtained by adding time 1 to the reference time.
2. Time T2 is obtained by adding time 2 to the reference time.
3. For analysis products time 1 will be zero and the time range code will be zero.
4. For initialised products time 1 will be zero and the time range code will be 1.
5. For forecast products time 1 will indicate the forecast period; the reference time will be the valid time of the initial data on which the forecast was based. (Time range code will be zero.)
6. Provision is made to extend time 1 over two octets to assist with extended range forecasts.
7. When time range code is 3 (i.e. average quantity) the number of quantities averaged will appear in octets 22 and 23 as a numerical value.

GRIB Edition 1

Code	Meaning
0	Forecast product valid for reference time +P1 (P1>0), or uninitialised analysis product for reference time (P1=0), or image product for reference time (P1=0)
1	Initialised analysis produce for reference time (P1=0)
2	Product with a valid time ranging between reference time +P1 and reference time +P2
3	Average (reference time +P1 to reference time +P2)
4	Accumulation (reference time +P1 to reference time +P2) product considered valid at reference time +P2
5	Difference (reference time +P2 minus reference time +P1) product considered valid at reference time +P2
6	
.	Reserved
9	
10	P1 occupies octets 19 and 20; product valid at reference time +P1
11	
.	Reserved

112	
113	Average of N forecasts (or initialised analyses); each product has forecast period of P1 (P1=0 for initialised analyses); products have reference times at intervals of P2, beginning at the given reference time.
114	Accumulation of N forecasts (or initialised analyses); each product has forecast period of P1 (P1=0 for initialised analyses); products have reference times at intervals of P2, beginning at the given reference time.
115	Average of N forecasts, all with the same reference time; the first has a forecast period of P1, the remaining forecasts follow at intervals of P2.
116	Accumulation of N forecasts, all with the same reference time; the first has a forecast period of P1, the remaining forecasts follow at intervals of P2.
117	Average of N forecasts; the first has a forecast period of P1, the subsequent ones have forecast periods reduced from the previous one by an interval of P2; the reference time for the first is given in octets 13 to 17, the subsequent ones have reference times increased from the previous one by an interval of P2. Thus all the forecasts have the same valid time, given by the initial reference time +P1.
118	
.	Reserved
122	
123	Average of N uninitialised analyses, starting at the reference time, at intervals of P2
124	Accumulations of N uninitialised analyses, starting at the reference time, at intervals of P2
125	
.	Reserved
254	

NOTES:

1. For analysis products, or the first of a series of analysis products, the reference time (octets 13 to 17) indicates the valid time.
2. For forecast products, or the first of a series of forecast products, the reference time indicates the valid time of the analysis upon which the (first) forecast is based.
3. Initialised analysis products are allocated code numbers distinct from those allocated to uninitialised analysis products.
4. Code figure 10 allows the period of a forecast to be extended over two octets; this is to assist with extended range forecasts.
5. Where products or a series of products are averaged or accumulated, the number involved is to be represented in octets 22 and 23 of Section 1, while any number missing is to be represented in octet 24.

6. Forecasts of the accumulation or difference of some quantity (e.g. quantitative precipitation forecasts), indicated by values of 4 or 5 in octet 21, have a product valid time given by the reference time +P2; the period of accumulation, or a difference, can be calculated as P2-P1.

7. A few examples may help to clarify the use of Code table 5:
For analysis products, P1 will be zero and the time range indicator will also be zero; for initialised products (sometimes called "zero hour forecasts"), P1 will be zero, but octet 21 will be set to 1. For forecasts, typically, P1 will contain the number of hours of the forecast (the unit indicator given in octet 18 would be 1) and octet 21 would contain a zero.
Code value 115 would be used, typically, for multiple day mean forecasts, all derived from the same initial conditions.
Code value 117 would be used, typically, for Monte Carlo type calculations: many forecasts valid at the same time from different initial (reference) times.
Averages, accumulations and differences get a somewhat specialised treatment. If octet 21 (Code table 5) has a value between 2 and 5 (Inclusive), then the reference time +P1 is the initial date/time and the reference time +P2 is the final date/time of the period over which averaging and accumulation takes place. If, however, octet 21 has a value of 113, 114, 115, 116, 117, 123 or 124, then P2 specifies the time interval between each of the fields (or the forecast initial times) that have been averaged or accumulated. These latter values of octet 21 require the qualities averaged to be equally separated in time; the former values, 3 and 4 in particular, allow for irregular or unspecified intervals of time between the fields that are averaged or accumulated.

TABLE 6: Data representation type

GRIB Experimental Edition

Code	Meaning
0	Latitude/longitude grid
1	Mercator projection
2	Stereographic projection
3	Lambert conformal projection
4	Gaussian latitude/longitude grid
	...
50	Spherical harmonic coefficients

GRIB Edition 0

Code	Meaning
0	Latitude/longitude grid
1	Mercator projection
2	Stereographic projection
3	Lambert conformal projection
4	Gaussian latitude/longitude grid
5)	
.)	Reserved
49)	
50	Spherical harmonic coefficients
51)	
.)	Reserved
254)	

GRIB Edition 1

Code	Meaning
0	Latitude/longitude grid - equidistant cylindrical or Plate Carée projection
1	Mercator projection
2	Gnomonic projection
3	Lambert conformal, secant or tangent, conic or bi-polar, projection
4	Gaussian latitude/longitude grid
5	Polar stereographic projection
6	Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) projection
7	Simple polyconic projection
8	Albers equal-area, secant or tangent, conic or bi-polar, projection
9	Miller's cylindrical projection
10	Rotated latitude/longitude grid
11	
.	
12	
13	Oblique Lambert conformal, secant or tangent, conic or bi-polar, projection
14	Rotated Gaussian latitude/longitude grid
15	
.	Reserved
19	
20	Stretched latitude/longitude grid
21	
.	
23	
24	Stretched Gaussian latitude/longitude grid
25	
.	Reserved
29	

30	Stretched and rotated latitude/longitude grids
31	
.	Reserved
33	
34	Stretched and rotated Gaussian latitude/longitude grids
35	
.	Reserved
49	
50	Spherical harmonic coefficients
51	
.	Reserved
59	
60	Rotated spherical harmonic coefficients
61	
.	Reserved
69	
70	Stretched spherical harmonics
71	
.	Reserved
79	
80	Stretched and rotated spherical harmonic coefficients
81	
.	Reserved
89	
90	Space view, perspective or orthographic
91	
.	Reserved
254	

TABLE 7: Resolution and components flag

GRIB Experimental Edition

Code	Meaning
1	Direction increments given
2	Latitude/longitude of extreme point given
3	Both given

GRIB Edition 0

Bit	Value	Meaning
1	0	Directions increments not given
	1	Direction increments given
2-8	0	Reserved

NOTE: Bits enumerated from left to right.

GRIB Edition 1

Bit	Value	Meaning
1	0	Direction increments not given
	1	Direction increments given
2	0	Earth assumed spherical with radius 6367.47km
	1	Earth assumed oblate spheroidal with size as determined by IAU in 1965 (6378.160 km, 6356.775 km, $f=1/297.0$)
3-4		Reserved
5	0	Resolved u- and v-components of vector quantities relative to easterly and northerly directions.
	1	Resolved u- and v-components of vector quantities relative to the defining grid in the direction of increasing x and y (or i and j) coordinates respectively

TABLE 8: Grid point scanning mode

GRIB Experimental Edition

Code	Meaning
0	Points scan from East to West. Points scan from North to South. Adjacent points on latitude circles are consecutive.
1	Points scan from West to East. Points scan from North to South. Adjacent points on latitude circles are consecutive.
2	Points scan from East to West. Points scan from South to North. Adjacent points on latitude circles are consecutive.
3	Points scan from West to East. Points scan from South to North. Adjacent points on latitude circles are consecutive.
4	Points scan from East to West. Points scan from North to South. Adjacent points on meridional circles are consecutive.
5	Points scan from West to East. Points scan from North to South. Adjacent points on meridional circles are consecutive.
6	Points scan from East to West. Points scan from South to North. Adjacent points on meridional circles are consecutive.
7	Points scan from West to East. Points scan from South to North. Adjacent points on meridional circles are consecutive.

GRIB Edition 0

Bit patterns (1,2, 3)	Meaning
000	Points scan from West to East. Points scan from North to South. Adjacent points on latitude circles are consecutive.

100	Points scan from East to West. Points scan from North to South. Adjacent points on latitude circles are consecutive.
010	Points scan from West to East. Points scan from South to North. Adjacent points on latitude circles are consecutive.
110	Points scan from East to West. Points scan from South to North. Adjacent points on latitude circles are consecutive.
001	Points scan from West to East. Points scan from North to South. Adjacent points on meridional circles are consecutive.
101	Points scan from East to West. Points scan from North to South. Adjacent points on meridional circles are consecutive.
011	Points scan from West to East. Points scan from South to North. Adjacent points on meridional circles are consecutive.
111	Points scan from East to West. Points scan from South to North. Adjacent points on meridional circles are consecutive.

NOTE: Bits enumerated from left to right.

GRIB Edition 1

Bit	Value	Meaning
1	0	Points scan in +i direction
	1	Points scan in -i direction
2	0	Points scan in -j direction
	1	Points scan in +j direction
3	0	Adjacent points in i direction are consecutive
	1	Adjacent points in j direction are consecutive

NOTES:

1. **i direction: west to east along a parallel, or left to right along an X-axis**
2. **j direction: south to north along a meridian, or bottom to top along a Y-axis**

TABLE 9: Spectral data representation type

All Editions

Code	Meaning
1	<p>The associated Legendre Functions of the first kind are defined by</p> $P_n^m(\mu) = \sqrt{(2n+1) \frac{(n-m)!}{(n+m)!}} \cdot \frac{1}{2^n n!} (1-\mu^2)^{\frac{m}{2}} \frac{d^{n+m}}{d\mu^{n+m}} (\mu^2-1)^n, (m \geq 0)$ $P_n^{-m}(\mu) = P_n^m(\mu)$ <p>A field $X(\lambda, \mu)$ is represented by</p> $X(\lambda, \mu) = \sum_{m=-M}^M \sum_{n= m }^{N(m)} X_n^m \cdot P_n^m(\mu) \cdot e^{im\lambda}$ <p>where λ is longitude, $\mu = \sin(\text{latitude})$, and X_n^{-m} = complex conjugate of X_n^m</p>

TABLE 10: Spectral data representation mode

All Editions

Code	Meaning
1	<p>The complex numbers X_n^m (see Table 9 above) are stored for $m \geq 0$ as pairs of real numbers $Re(X_n^m), Im(X_n^m)$ ordered with n increasing from m to $N(m)$, first for $m = 0$ and then for $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$. The real part of the $(0, 0)$ coefficient is stored in octets 12-15 of the binary data block. The imaginary part of the $(0, 0)$ coefficient and the remaining coefficients are packed, and are stored in octets 16 onwards of the binary data block.</p>

TABLE 11: Flag (first 4 bits only)**GRIB Experimental Edition**

Code	Meaning
0	Grid point data - packed binary data begins at octet 12
1	Spherical harmonic coefficients - packed binary data begins at octet 16

GRIB Edition 0

Bit	Value	Meaning
1	0	Grid point data - packed binary data begins at octet 12
	1	spherical harmonic coefficients - packed binary data begins at octet 16
2-4	0	Reserved

NOTE: Bits enumerated from left to right.

GRIB Edition 1

Bit	Value	Meaning
1	0	Grid point data
	1	Spherical harmonic coefficients
2	0	Simple packing
	1	Complex or second-order packing
3	0	Floating point values (in the original data) are represented
	1	Integer values (in the original data) are represented
4	0	No additional flags at octet 14
	1	Octet 14 contains additional flag bits
5		Reserved (set to 0)

6	0	Single datum at each grid point
	1	Matrix of values at each grid point
7	0	No secondary bit maps
	1	Secondary bit maps present
8	0	Second-order values constant width
	1	Second-order values different widths
9-12		Reserved for future use

Notes:

- 1 Bit 4 shall be set to 1 to indicate that bits 5 to 12 are contained in octet 14 of the Binary data section.
- 2 Bit 3 shall be set to 1 to indicate that the data represented are integer values; where integer values are represented, any reference values, if not zero, should be rounded to integer before being applied.
- 3 Where secondary bit maps are present in the data (used in association with second order packing and, optionally, with a matrix of values at each point), this shall be indicated by setting bit 7 to 1.

APPENDIX • F ECMWF LOCAL EXTENSIONS TO SECTION 1 GRIB CODE

ECMWF local GRIB use definition 1

Octet Number	Contents
41	Local definition number: 1
42	Class: 1 = Operations 2 = Research
43	Type: 1 = First Guess 2 = Analysis 3 = Initialised analysis 4 = OI analysis 5 = 3D variational analysis 6 = 4D variational analysis 7 = 3D variational analysis 8 = 4D variational analysis 9 = Forecast 10 = Control forecast 11 = Perturbed forecast 12 = Errors in first guess 13 = Errors in analysis 14 = Cluster means 15 = Cluster standard deviations 17 = Ensemble means 18 = Ensemble standard deviations 20 = Climatology 30 = Observations 31 = Quality control 32 = Difference statistics 40 = Image data
44-45	Stream: 50 = Meteosat 3 51 = Meteosat 4 201 = NOAA 9 250 = GOES 6 251 = GOES 7 1025 = Daily archive 1035 = Ensemble forecasts 1041 = TOGA 1042 = Chernobyl 1043 = Monthly 1044 = Supplementary data 1045 = Wave 1046 = Ocean 1050 = Bracknell 1051 = Washington 1052 = Offenbach 1053 = Paris 1054 = Tokyo 1055 = Montreal 1060 = Test
46-49	Expver: Version number or experiment identifier

50	Number:	Ensemble forecast number Control forecast is number 0 perturbed forecasts 1-nn Set to 0, if not ensemble forecast
51	Total:	Total number of forecasts in ensemble This number includes the control forecast Set to 0, if not ensemble forecast
52	Reserved.	Set to 0

ECMWF LOCAL GRIB USE DEFINITION 2

Octet Number	Contents
41	Local definition number :- 2
42-49	As for definition 1
50	Number:- Cluster number
51	Total :- Total number of clusters
52	Reserved. Set to 0
53	Clustering method: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 - maximum linkage method 2 - mixed method 3 - small linkage method
54-55	Start time step considered when clustering
56-57	End time step considered when clustering (same units of time as forecast timesteps)
58-60	Northern latitude of domain of clustering
61-63	Western longitude of domain of clustering
64-66	Southern latitude of domain of clustering
67-69	Eastern longitude of domain of clustering (In units of millidegrees)
70	Number of cluster to which operational forecast belongs
71	Number of cluster to which control forecast belongs
72	N:- Number of forecasts belonging to the cluster, including the control forecast
73-328	n-n:- List of N ensemble forecast numbers. Any unused octets at end of list set to 0.

ECMWF LOCAL GRIB USE DEFINITION 5

Octet Number	Contents
41	Local definition number : 5 - Forecast probabilities.
42	Class : 1 = Operations
43	Type : 16 = Forecast probabilities

44-45	Stream: 1035 = Ensemble forecasts
46-49	Expver: Version number (1).
50	Forecast probability number. See note 1.
51	Total number of Forecast probabilities.
52	Threshold units decimal scale factor (D). See note 2. Negative value is indicated by setting the high-order bit (bit 1) to 1 (on).
53	Threshold indicator. See note 3. 1 = Lower threshold only 2 = Upper threshold only 3 = Upper and lower thresholds
54-55	Lower threshold
56-57	Upper threshold
58	Reserved. Set to 0.

APPENDIX • G MARS WORKSTATION FOR MEMBER STATES

Overview

This documentation describes the new features introduced in Mars on the workstation. The program is a complete redesign of the client side of the Mars system. The server side (running on the IBM) remains unchanged for the time being.

Major changes

- **Switches** Mars workstation understands most of the existing requests, but will ignore all the UNICOS switches (like -f, -o,...).
- **Unsupported verbs** HELP, NEWS, CHECKOUT, STATUS, QUIT. Although they can be implemented, their use is being reviewed.
- **Optional verb** END. This verb is no longer compulsory. If it is present, MARS will ignore the following requests.
- **New verbs** READ, WRITE, COMPUTE. The verb READ is actually defined on the CRAY version, as a command to include more directives.
- **New concept** The FIELDSET parameter in the RETRIEVE command.
- **Binary data** All files created by Mars workstation are pure binary. You need to use some utility routines described in Meteorological Bulletin M1.9/4 to access this data
- **Interpolation** Mars workstation uses the new MARSINT interpolation software so results are slightly different to those obtained on the Cray.

Minor changes

Some minor changes have been introduced, such as allowing the use of TO and BY for every list (such as LEVELIST=1/TO/31).

Lines can now be commented using the # symbol (like most unix files, such as shell scripts or makefiles). The * is still supported as a comment symbol, but only in the first column.

There is no longer the restriction that only U and V wind components or Vorticity and Divergence can be retrieved in a single request.

Fieldsets

Fieldsets

In order to introduce formulae in MARS, a new concept has been added: the *fieldset*. A fieldset can be compared to a FORTRAN variable. It is a name used to represent a *collection of several fields*. Any name may be given to a fieldset. There are four MARS verbs that use fieldsets:

RETRIEVE

The following request:

```
RETRIEVE,  
  DATE      = -1,  
  LEVEL     = 1000/500/250,  
  PARAM     = Z,  
  FIELDSET  = A
```

defines a fieldset named A containing 3 fields (z1000,z500,z250). The order of the fields in the fieldset is the standard MARS order and is described in the MARS manual.

Note that the TARGET parameter can be used in conjunction with the FIELDSET parameter.

READ

A fieldset can be read from an existing Unix file:

```
READ,  
  FIELDSET  = A,  
  SOURCE    = "myfile"
```

or from a CFS file:

```
READ,  
  FIELDSET  = A,  
  CFSPATH   = "/me/myfile"
```

COMPUTE

The compute command is fully described later.

WRITE

A fieldset can be written into a target file:

```
WRITE,  
  FIELDSET  = A,  
  TARGET    = "myf"
```


Technical considerations

This chapter explains some of the technical details of mars.

Networking MARS

This version of MARS is fully networked. MARS will query several databases to get the requested data.

The databases are scanned in the following order:

- **Main MCS** MCS stands for *MARS Caching System*. It is an *Empress* database sitting on a server. Each time a field is retrieved from the IBM, it is copied there. The next time this field is requested, MARS will find it in this database. The management of this database is automatic, and rarely used fields are removed first. This database is presently on *munin* and is 2 Gigabytes large
- **Cray FDB** The FDB is accessed only if the request is for the most recent analysis or forecast data.
- **IBM** This is of course the main archive. The IBM is also capable of doing some of the post-processing. Note that there are only 9 concurrent users on the IBM, so requests may queue.

NFS

NFS is the protocol used to share files among all workstations and servers at ECMWF. Users logging in to any of the machines find their normal environment. NFS was designed to share small files such as the dot files (*.login*, *.cshrc*, ...) and home directory. Trying to use NFS to move a lot a data will kill the network.

This request retrieves 2 Megabytes of data: the target is on the home directory, which is on odin

```
mars - INFO - Request 1 is :
```

```
RETRIEVE,  
  CLASS      = OD,  
  TYPE       = IA,  
  STREAM     = DA,  
  EXPVER     = 1,  
  LEVTYPE    = PL,  
  LEVELIST   = 1000/850/700/500/400/300,  
  REPRES     = SH,  
  DOMAIN     = G,  
  PARAM      = 129/130/131/132,  
  DATE       = 931025,  
  TIME       = 1200,  
  STEP       = 00,  
  TARGET     = "myfile",  
  GRID       = 1.5/1.5
```

```
mars - INFO - 24 fields retrieved from 'MAIN MCS'  
mars - INFO - Request time: wall: 1 min 20 sec  
mars - INFO - No errors reported
```

Now the same request, but the target file is on local disk on ecgate1:

```
mars - INFO - Request 1 is :
```

```
RETRIEVE,  
  CLASS      = OD,  
  TYPE       = IA,  
  STREAM     = DA,  
  EXPVER     = 1,  
  LEVTYPE    = PL,  
  LEVELIST   = 1000/850/700/500/400/300,  
  REPRES     = SH,  
  DOMAIN     = G,  
  PARAM      = 129/130/131/132,  
  DATE       = 931025,  
  TIME       = 1200,  
  STEP       = 00,  
  TARGET     = "/tmp/myfile",  
  GRID       = 1.5/1.5
```

```
mars - INFO - 24 fields retrieved from 'MAIN MCS'  
mars - INFO - Request time: wall: 6 sec  
mars - INFO - No errors reported
```

As you can see, the first time the request took 1 minute and 20 seconds, the second time it took only 6 seconds. The 1 minute and 14 seconds difference is spent trying to write the data back to the NFS server. Scripts in /home/us/ust/doc/user/ecgate1 (retpak and retobs) show how to retrieve data to target file in /tmp on ecgate1.

COMPUTE

Introduction

A new command has been added to help users do some field manipulations. Any mathematical computation can be done on retrieved grid point GRIB fields.

```
COMPUTE,  
  FIELDSET = Z,  
  FORMULA  = "X/2+log(Y)*X"
```

In this example, X and Y are two fieldsets, Z is the output fieldset.

Conventions

- X upper case characters denote fieldsets
- X^k is the k^{th} element of fieldset X
- X_{ij}^k is point column i line j of field X^k
- a lower case characters are real scalars
- '...' is a character string
- f (...) is a function call
- FORMULA (...) is the mars FORMULA

What is actually computed

Any mathematical formula can be reduced to a series of elementary computations involving only one or two values. So the formula in the introduction can be reduced to:

- [1] compute $X/2$
- [2] compute $\log(Y)$
- [3] compute $[2]*X$
- [4] compute $[1]+[3]$

For each of the fields X^k and Y^k of X and Y, a field Z^k is computed using the FORMULA and added to the fieldset Z.

Mixing fields and scalars

If the two operands are two fields, the operation is carried out between each pair of corresponding grid points of the two fields. The result is a field.

If one operand is a scalar and the other a field, the operation is carried out between each grid point and the scalar. The result is a field.

If the two operands are two scalars, the result is a scalar.

Calling functions

The same logic applies to functions. If the argument of a function is a field, the result is a field where each grid point is the result of the function at the corresponding grid point in the input field.

If the argument is a scalar the output is also a scalar.

Examples

```
COMPUTE,
  FIELDSET = X,
  FORMULA  = "A * B"
```

Creates a fieldset X where $X_{ij}^k = A_{ij}^k * B_{ij}^k$. Note that * is a scalar multiplication, not a matrix multiplication.

```
COMPUTE,
  FIELDSET = X,
  FORMULA  = "A * 2"
```

Creates a fieldset X where $X_{ij}^k = A_{ij}^k * 2$

```
COMPUTE,
  FIELDSET = X,
  FORMULA  = "(A>10) * B + (A<=10)*C"
```

Creates a fieldset X where:

- $X_{ij}^k = B_{ij}^k$ if $A_{ij}^k > 10$
- $X_{ij}^k = C_{ij}^k$ if $A_{ij}^k \leq 10$

Operators

The following operators are implemented:

Boolean operators

- = equal to
- > greater than
- < less than
- >= greater or equal to
- <= less than or equal to
- <> not equal to

All the boolean operators return 1 if the test is true, 0 otherwise.

Arithmetic operators

- + addition
- - subtraction
- * multiplication
- / division
- ^ power

The sign '-' can also be used to denote negation. In this case it is actually a function not an operator.

Functions

The functions are described in detail in the next chapter.

Sub fieldsets

You can extract fields from a fieldset using the square brackets. If X is a fieldset, $X[2]$ is the second field, $X[1, 10]$ is the first 10 fields and $X[2, 8, 2]$ is every second field of X starting from 2 up to 8.

Order of precedence

Mars will follow the mathematical order of operations:

- function calls
- ^
- * and /
- + and -
- boolean operators

By using brackets, you can change the order of computation.

Functions

Mathematical functions

Table 1: Mathematical functions

Name	# of param.	Param. type	Result type	Description
max	any	any	fieldset if one of the parameters is a fieldset, scalar otherwise	Maximum
min	any	any	fieldset if one of the parameters is a fieldset, scalar otherwise	Minimum
sgn	1	any	same as parameter	0 if the value is 0, +1 if the value is positive, -1 if the value is negative.
int	1	any	same as parameter	Integer part
exp	1	any	same as parameter	Exponential
log	1	any	same as parameter	Natural logarithm
sin	1	any	same as parameter	Sine
cos	1	any	same as parameter	Cosine
tan	1	any	same as parameter	Tangent
asin	1	any	same as parameter	Arc-sine
acos	1	any	same as parameter	Arc-cosine
atan	1	any	same as parameter	Arc-tangent
abs	1	any	same as parameter	Absolute value
sqrt	1	any	same as parameter	Square root

Table 1: Mathematical functions

Name	# of param.	Param. type	Result type	Description
count	1	fieldset	scalar	Number of fields in the fieldset
sum	1	fieldset	1 field	Sum of all the fields in the fieldset.
mean	1	fieldset	1 field	Mean of all the fields in the fieldset.
rms	1	fieldset	1 field	Root mean square of all the fields in the fieldset.
stdev	1	fieldset	1 field	Standard deviation of all the fields in the fieldset.

Future

Any functions could be added if there is a need for them. Maybe some useful physical and mathematical constants will also be introduced.

To a MARS request:

```
#
# Retrieve z1000...
#
retrieve,
  date      = -1,
  param     = z,
  fieldset  = z1000,
  levelist  = 1000,
  grid      = 3/3
#
# ...and z850
#
retrieve,
  fieldset  = z850,
  levelist  = 850
#
# Compute...
#
compute,
  fieldset  = meant,
  formula   = "-(9.8/8.3) * (log(z850) - log(z1000)) / (log(850) - log(1000))"
```

Warnings

No check is done on the type of data combined in the formulae. It is the user's responsibility to make sure the computations have a physical meaning.

At the present time the GRIB header of the resulting fields is wrong (it is copied from the first field encountered) as there is no GRIB definition for compound fields (well, not yet).